

'Meet the Cast': An ethnographic exploration of creative self-awareness exercises combined with how performance-inspired practical tools can be used to increase confidence with public speaking.

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Abstract

Context

The study explored whether an increase in self-awareness coupled with an awareness of relevant practical tools can lead to an increase in confidence with public speaking. A package of four person-centred wellbeing sessions were constructed to include creative and performance-inspired practical exercises and an Episodic Simulation of a positive public speaking experience.

Approach

Creative exercises were inspired by the foundational principles of Richard Schwartz's Internal Family Systems (IFS) approach and were designed to increase self-awareness by *identifying* and *separating* parts of the 'self' involved in perceptions of public speaking, before compassionately *accepting* these parts and *transforming* perceptions. Each session, which involved breathwork, muscle relaxation and guided visualisation, took place in participants' imaginary 'Inner Stage' which they were guided to create as an internal workspace. These drama-inspired workshop exercises allowed participants to develop a practical toolkit for use in real-life settings.

Findings

As a result of the study, all nine participants experienced an increase in self-awareness and self-confidence as evidenced by ethnographic reflections and quantitative assessment tools, thus enhancing everyday lived experience in the workplace and beyond. The study concluded that an increase in self-awareness achieved using IFS-inspired creative exercises, alongside the development of performance-inspired practical skills, can lead to an increase in confidence with public speaking. As a result of the study, some criticisms levelled at IFS have been addressed by providing evidence of its effectiveness.

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Key Terms and Definitions

Below are some key terms used throughout the study and a brief definition of each. Expanded definitions and descriptions are located in Chapter 2: Literature Review.

Character Creation Exercise: An original creative exercise inspired by Internal Family Systems (IFS) principles designed to help participants increase self-awareness by using their own lived experiences to create and develop characters. Please also see the term Internal Family Systems (IFS).

Compassion Focused Therapy (CFT): CFT is a therapeutic approach created by Professor Paul Gilbert which promotes the development of self-compassion as a way of navigating life's challenges.

Diaphragmatic Breathing (DB): DB is a deep breathing technique used to promote relaxation and nervous system regulation.

Episodic Simulation (ES): ES refers to the ability to construct mental images in the mind's eye. Please also see the key term 'Guided Visualisation.'

Guided Visualisation (GV): GV, also referred to as Guided Imagery (GI), is a technique in which a person is guided to use their imagination to create visual images or scenarios.

Inner Stage: An imaginary theatre stage that participants were guided to create in their mind's eye. This provided a positive internal environment which was re-visited during each session during creative and practical exercises.

Internal Family Systems Approach (IFS): IFS is a therapeutic approach developed by Richard Schwartz which helps individuals identify and work therapeutically with the different parts of their inner psyche to heal inner conflicts.

Progressive Muscle Relaxation (PMR): PMR is a relaxation technique in which muscles are systematically tensed and relaxed to reduce stress and anxiety.

Chapter 1: Introduction

“There’s a lot of stuff out there on presenting, or how to come across in meetings, but they are not centred within the person, or self-reflective [...] they just build up your confidence for that meeting, or that presentation, without working holistically on the self.” – Participant 3

Communicating with others is an essential part of the human experience, vital for our survival. Humans are designed to connect with others and our ability to communicate can enhance this sense of connection, and help us feel understood, accepted, and supported (Gilbert, 2013). In a world dependent on communication, many people experience difficulties when it comes to speaking with others, particularly in formal settings and when asked to communicate and present ideas (Tsaousides, 2017; North, 2020). According to LeMind (2014), the fear of speaking publicly ranked third in the top ten most common fears, falling just behind a fear of death (second) and a fear of loneliness (first).

Fear of public speaking has been widely researched (Benkhe and Sawyerm 2001; Bodie, 2010; Tsaousides 2017; Genard, 2019; Jean-Pierre, Hassan and Sturge, 2023), and literature offering techniques to improve confidence with public speaking is wide-ranging, from scientific studies exploring the benefits of exposure therapy (Finn, Sawyer and Schrod, 2009) to inspiring Ted Talks (TED Masterclass Team, 2020) to tips from popular self-help gurus such as Tony Robbins (Robbins, 2023).

1.1 Self-awareness and Internal Family Systems (IFS)

As a researcher, I am particularly interested in the role of self-awareness during public speaking activities. My academic background lies in Performance, Psychology and holistic approaches to health and wellbeing.¹ I became interested in self-awareness and the importance of knowing and understanding oneself during my academic study of Psychology. Several years later whilst attending training for holistic wellbeing qualifications, I was introduced to the Internal Family Systems (IFS) approach developed by Richard Schwartz.

¹ Please note that I refer to the Dictionary.com definition of holistic as “concerned with the care of the entire person in all aspects of well-being, including the physical, psychological, and social, rather than with diseases and symptoms in isolation” (Dictionary.com). In the context of this study, the word holistic is used to convey an approach that looks that the mind and body as whole.

The IFS model proposes that the mind is not 'one' mind, rather it is comprised of various sub-minds, referred to as 'parts' (Schwartz, 2013). These can be representations of thoughts, feelings, and memories (Hodgdon, *et al.*, 2022), each with their own way of engaging with their environment (Lester, 2017). The goals of individual parts will often conflict and create an inner tension (Hsieh, 2015); Schwartz argues that we can *identify* and *separate* these different parts, and by learning to *accept* the different parts, we can work towards *transforming* our beliefs and consequently resolve inner conflicts.

The present study adopted the IFS the principles of *identify*, *separate*, *accept* and *transform*, and applied them in a creative way, alongside performance-inspired practical exercises, to explore whether this could increase self-awareness, and lead to a subsequent increase in self-confidence with public speaking.

The IFS approach is becoming increasingly popular as a therapeutic intervention, however there is still a lack of empirical evidence of its utility (Earleywine *et al.*, 2024; Brownstone, Hunsinker and Greene, 2024). The present study sought to address this criticism and demonstrate that key principles of the IFS approach can be effective at increasing self-awareness and self-confidence with public speaking tasks when applied in a creative way. As a result of the study, all participants experienced an increase in self-awareness and self-confidence with regards to public speaking, thus providing evidence in support of the utility of the IFS approach in a creative context.

Although some themes explored within present study may also be researched within the context of dramatherapy, it should be noted that I am not a trained Drama Therapist thus did not seek ethical approval to conduct any therapeutic interventions. As such, the review of literature excludes dramatherapy theory. Instead, I chose to explore confidence in public speaking through a creative and performance-inspired lens using a person-centred approach with participant wellbeing at the heart.

1.2 Aims and Objectives

The study aimed to explore whether an increase in self-awareness, coupled with an awareness of relevant practical tools, could lead to a perceived increase in self-confidence towards public speaking.

A package of four person-centred interactive sessions was created that served as a vehicle to fulfil the following objectives:

- 1) To increase self-awareness using a Character Creation exercise inspired by the Internal Family Systems approach.

The Character Creation exercise was designed to increase self-awareness by helping participants to *identify, separate* and *accept* the parts of their 'self' in relation to their perception public speaking, and to *transform* their perception about their perceived level of confidence.

- 2) To create a hybrid practical toolkit that participants can use to soothe and ground themselves when preparing for public speaking activities.

This was achieved by combining holistic wellbeing tools such as diaphragmatic breathing, muscle relaxation and guided visualisation, with techniques used by performers such as facial muscle and vocal warm-ups, the use of physicality, and character observation.

- 3) To use future-focused Episodic Simulation to give participants a positive experience of a possible future public speaking activity.

A mixed methods approach was adopted in which the data gathered was primarily qualitative comprising of personal reflections from participants about their experiences throughout the sessions, reflections of homework tasks, and reflections during a semi-structured interview held post-study. Quantitative measures of public speaking anxiety and perceived confidence levels were used at both the beginning and end of the study.

As this was a creative exploration as opposed to a therapeutic intervention, the study was aimed at participants who experienced relative discomfort when speaking formally, and wished to improve their confidence in this area, but who did not have specific anxiety conditions or clinical diagnoses.

1.3 Chapter Summary

The following text provides a summary of subsequent chapters to help the reader navigate the remainder of the thesis.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

This chapter provides the reader with an understanding of the key concepts explored within the study supported by the relevant literature. These include the fear of public speaking; the core principles of the Internal Family Systems model (*Identify, Separate, Accept* and *Transform*) and how they were applied within the study; key session components of Progressive Muscle Relaxation (PMR),

Diaphragmatic Breathing (DB) and Guided Visualisation (GV); drama-inspired practical exercises, and relevant performance theory from Erving Goffman and Konstantin Stanislavski.

Chapter 3: Methodology

This chapter provides the reader with an understanding of the methodological principles guiding the study and utility for participants. This is followed by a discussion of the qualitative method of Ethnography, and the quantitative assessment tools, the Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA) and Self-Report of Confidence. Finally, the reader is provided with the research design including a step-by-step guide to the practical sessions conducted within the study and an explanation of how the data was analysed using Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA).

Chapter 4: Findings and Discussion

This chapter presents the ethnographic findings in case study format, and the quantitative findings presented in table format, and demonstrates that all participants experienced an increase in self-awareness and self-confidence after taking part in the study. Findings are grouped and organised under the headings of the IFS principles (*Identify, Separate, Accept and Transform*) and include interim discussions and conclusions at each point. The chapter concludes with a discussion of the limitations of the study and how these may be addressed in future studies.

Chapter 5: Conclusions

This final chapter summarises the findings and the relevance of the study within the wider academic field, namely that it contributes evidence to the effectiveness of the IFS approach, thus addressing a key criticism that there is a lack of evidence in support of the utility of it. The chapter closes with a discussion of how the present study could be developed by converting the sessions into group workshop format.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1: Fear of Public Speaking

The fear of speaking in public ranked third in the Top 10 common fears (LeMind, 2014), suggesting that many people experience anxiety at the thought of public speaking. Anxiety is a natural biological response that serves to activate the body's flight or fight response, preparing us psychologically and physiologically to either flee from perceived danger, or stay and 'fight' (Wilczynska *et al.*, 2019; Torales *et al.*, 2020). We have evolved with this threat system as a way of keeping us safe (Gilbert, 2013), however the system can become maladaptive when our assessment of the perceived threat is disproportionate, leading to an impairment in daily functioning (Torales *et al.*, 2020). Public Speaking Anxiety (PSA) has been studied in-depth (Bodie, 2010). Whilst this study does not directly concern those clinically diagnosed with PSA, understanding the experience of those at the extreme end of the scale provides a useful context for this study.

Many of those affected may simply experience mild discomfort and awkwardness, however in more extreme cases, individuals may experience the condition 'Glossophobia,' in which individuals experience intense physiological sensations such as heart palpitations, nausea, and vomiting (Montijo, 2022), as well as worrisome intrusive thoughts about speaking publicly (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Others, however, may fall somewhere in between, commonly experiencing shaking, trembling, shortness of breath, accompanied by negative beliefs about audience evaluation (Genard, 2019; North, 2020).

According to Tsaousides (2017), theorists have discovered four distinct factors that contribute to the fear of speaking in formal settings; physiology, thoughts, skills, and situations (Bodie, 2010). *Physiologically*, the autonomic nervous system enters a state of hyperarousal in response to a perceived threat and prepares us for "battle" by inciting our 'Flight or Fight' response, which, as Tsaousides suggests, can impact our ability to speak comfortably to an audience. Cognitively, an individual may experience ruminative *thoughts* and negative beliefs about oneself as a speaker which can exacerbate the fear (Bodie, 2010) as well as negative beliefs about the audience judging them (Genard, 2019) and feeling unprepared can lead people to negatively judge their own *skillset* as a speaker. Genard also highlights that *situations* in which there is a degree of evaluation on our performance as a speaker can heighten anxiety. These four categories informed my decision on which practical tools and exercises to include in the study, and I addressed them in the following ways: *physiology* (breathwork, muscle relaxation and posture), *thoughts* (creative character exercises exploring their thoughts surrounding public speaking), *skills* (developing awareness of relevant skills)

and *situations* (a guided Episodic Simulation of a public speaking in a situation relevant to their individual lives).

Tsaousides (2017) argues that shifting the body from the flight or fight reaction, into a calm state can reduce anxiety. Relaxation techniques such as controlled breathwork (Genard, 2019) and Progressive Muscle Relaxation (PMR) can calm the nervous system and reduce anxiety (Cuncic, 2020). Jean-Pierre, Hassan and Sturge (2023) demonstrated that students tasked with preparing and delivering a three-minute lightning talk found frequent practice helpful, coupled with breathing exercises to assist emotional regulation. Guided imagery techniques can also promote relaxation (Altgassen *et al.*, 2015; Reeves *et al.*, 2022). As such, I decided to include Diaphragmatic Breathing, PMR and Guided Imagery as core components of every session.

2.2 Increasing Self-Awareness and the Internal Family Systems Approach

A key aim of the study was to increase self-awareness, with the view that this can subsequently increase self-confidence. Johnson (2022) argues that self-awareness is a must-have trait for public speakers and an understanding of personal strengths and weaknesses can help a speaker maximise their strengths and improve on their weaknesses.

Research regarding the specific role of self-awareness and confidence in public speaking is limited. An early study by Daly, Vangelisti and Lawrence (1989) suggested that negative public speaking experiences correlated with an increase in attention to the self, alongside negative evaluations of the self. Similarly, Shi, Brinthaupt and McCree (2015) discovered a positive relationship between the frequency of negative self-talk and public speaking anxiety. Similar research areas include the role of self-awareness in social anxiety (Bogels, Alberts and de Jong, 1996; George and Stopa, 2008), or the effects of self-focused rumination (Mellings and Alden, 2000).

The terms *self-awareness* and *self-perception* can both be used to describe getting to know the self. At the beginning of this study, most participants had the perception that they were not confident at public speaking. Approaches to help change negative self-perception are many, often based around changing thinking patterns, for example Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT; Gilbert, 2013). However, this study was non-therapeutic in nature and thus did not call for clinical interventions such as CBT. Rather the intention was to introduce creative ways to increase self-awareness.

The Internal Family Systems (IFS) model differs from behavioural approaches like CBT in that it aims to create positive self-perception through self-acceptance and compassion, which for some may be a more tolerable approach than rigorous behavioural techniques (Hodgdon *et al.*, 2022). The

foundational principles of IFS, alongside self-acceptance and compassion inspired the creative character exercises included in the sessions.

2.2.1: What is Internal Family Systems (IFS)?

Schwartz (2013) posits that the 'self' is comprised of multiple 'parts,' likened to an internal family, which can be comprised of contrasting beliefs and opinions and may result in inner conflict. He proposes that each person has a core 'Self' part, which acts as a compassionate inner leader of an internal family of parts. Alongside the Self, are 'Protector' parts, which help protect the individual from perceived threat, and 'Exile' parts which are often borne out of painful experiences (Hughes, Horton and Hamer, 2022). Tension is often created when parts have different goals and intentions; the IFS approach can help to relieve this tension by working towards identifying, and subsequently meeting, the needs of these individual parts.

The IFS model proposes that all parts are valuable and a valid part of a healthy mind² and as the title of his recent book suggests, there are *No Bad Parts* (Schwartz, 2021). Furthermore, we can learn to accept all parts of the self and view them as an internal 'family' interacting with each other. If we can treat these parts with compassion, it can lead to transformation (Schwartz, 2013).

This concept of subpersonalities is not new. A brief glance at history leads us to the early work of Sigmund Freud who proposed that our personality was formed of the ID, Ego and Superego (Rennison, 2015), and also the early work of Assagioli (1973) who was one of the first to argue that we are comprised of multiple personalities. Similarly, Jung (1991) proposed that within us exist as many as 12 different characters, or 'archetypes.' With a background in Jungian Psychology, Stone and Stone (1994) proposed that the personality consists of a group of primary selves, disowned selves, and protector selves, similar to the suggestion of Exiles and Protectors within the IFS model. Stone and Stone (1994) developed the Voice Dialogue approach which works with the individual parts that comprise the human psyche, enabling an individual to converse with aspects of their self and bring about balance and harmony within.

2.2.2: IFS at the Movies

With growing recognition and mainstream popularity, the IFS model has even been demonstrated in recent popular blockbuster movies. The Disney movie *Inside Out* is an excellent illustration of IFS, in

² The existence of internal sub-personalities can indicate clinical pathology, such as Dissociative Identity Disorder (NHS, 2023) and indeed severe trauma can lead to the personality becoming fractured. However, it is worth noting that this study was not clinical in nature, nor was it a therapeutic intervention and participants were made aware of this during the informed consent procedure. Rather the intention of this study was to use the IFS model as a theoretical inspiration for creative exercises designed to increase self-awareness and self-confidence in those who merely find it challenging to speak formally in public.

which the viewer sees the 11-year-old lead character's mind portrayed by characters which are based upon emotions Sadness, Anger, Fear, Disgust and Joy. These inner characters interact and ultimately form an internal family (Moore, 2018). The film demonstrates how the parts within us often have different emotions and belief systems, and how we can work with them to reach a state of harmony, much like the process within IFS.

Another example can be seen in the biopic movie *Rocketman*, about the life of Elton John. In the opening scene the viewer watches Elton John in a group therapy session dressed in a chicken costume interacting with significant members of his life who emerge around him, speaking dialogue from his own internal narrative. The viewer becomes aware that they are witnessing his internal thought processes that have arisen from his personal relationships as opposed to the individuals being physically present. According to Hughes, Horton and Hammer (2022), the scene is an excellent example of IFS therapy approaches in action, in which clients are actively encouraged to dialogue with the parts of themselves, parts that have so often been unconsciously shaped by their interactions with people in their lives.

2.2.3: Benefits of IFS

By adopting an IFS approach, we can get to know our own internal family of parts which can increase our self-awareness and help us navigate life with more self-compassion. The IFS approach has been used to treat a variety of clinical conditions. According to Shadick *et al.*, (2013) it is effective in treating pain in Rheumatoid Arthritis patients alongside traditional medical approaches. Furthermore, they demonstrated that IFS approach also led to increased self-compassion which improved psychological reactions to the experience of pain. IFS is also known to benefit those experiencing Multiple Sclerosis, migraines, and spinal pain (Shadick *et al.*, 2013) as well as personality disorders, eating disorders (Lister, 2017) and substance use disorders (Smith, Hayes and Jordan, 2019). Hodgdon *et al.*, (2022), who explored the impact of the IFS approach as treatment for childhood trauma, argue that it may provide a positive alternative to more cognitive based treatments. It has also been shown to help survivors of sexual abuse to make meaning out of their experiences (Miller, Cardona and Hardin, 2006).

The IFS approach can help therapists understand their own internal thought processes. A study by Mojta, Falconier and Huebner, (2014) explored the use of the IFS approach with novice therapists and found it enhanced therapist's self-awareness, which consequently strengthened the therapeutic relationship with their clients. When therapists disclosed to clients that they were working on their own thought processes, a deeper sense of trust was established, and it served as positive role-modelling. This was consistent with the suggestion of Schwartz (1995) who argued that therapists must model how to take responsibility for their own parts.

Although increasingly popular as a therapeutic intervention, a criticism of IFS is the notable lack of evidence-based literature despite its theories being established over thirty years ago (Brownstone, Hunsinker and Greene, 2024). This is particularly true for trauma interventions (Lucero, Jones and Hunsaker, 2018; Hodgdon *et al.*, 2022; Comeau *et al.*, 2024; Earleywine, *et al.*, 2024). Brownstone and colleagues argue that the application of IFS may even cause potential harm to some clinical groups, such as those with psychosis, as the process of viewing the self as multiple parts may create confusion in those with distorted perceptions of reality. This concern has also been highlighted in previous studies (Deacon and Davis, 2001, Lucero, Jones and Hunsaker, 2018). As such, it must be acknowledged that the IFS approach has not yet received adequate scientific scrutiny and is therefore lacking empirical support of its efficacy (Earleywine *et al.*, 2024).

During my own therapeutic journey using the IFS approach, I experienced first-hand the insights and self-awareness that can arise from working with individual parts of the self. It was this lived experience of understanding the mechanisms of the IFS approach that inspired me to devise the creative character exercises used in this study and facilitate them effectively.

2.3: The IFS Model in Practice

According to Schwartz (2013) the goal of IFS is to *identify* parts, *separate* the parts from each other, learn to *accept* them, then *transform* them.

This premise was the foundation for the character creation exercises, which were designed to help participants *identify* and *separate* parts of their 'self' in relation to public speaking. To allow for this identification and separation of the parts, participants were asked to create three characters. They were given a simple brief for each character that they had to create: 'Character 1' was uncomfortable with public speaking, 'Compassion' was unconditionally kind and accepting, and 'Protagonist' was confident and enjoyed public speaking. To help them create these characters, participants were invited to draw inspiration from their own lived experiences.

I specifically included themes of compassion to embody the element of *acceptance* of the parts of themselves that felt uncomfortable about public speaking. The subsequent sessions were designed to help participants progress towards *transformation*, in which their perception of speaking publicly would shift towards confidence.

When using the IFS approach in a therapeutic capacity, the parts tend to emerge organically, which is a highly individualised process. However, this study was not designed to be therapeutic in nature thus utilisation of the prescriptive therapeutic protocol was not required. Rather, the research sessions

were intended to be creative in nature, designed through a performance-based lens to increase self-awareness via creative exercises inspired by the foundational principles of IFS, alongside practical tools. In a research context it is important to ensure standardisation wherever possible. As such, rather than allow for participants' parts to emerge entirely organically as one would in a clinical context, I made the decision to create a standardised 'cast' of the three aforementioned characters: 'Character 1,' 'Compassion' and 'Protagonist.' This established a degree of standardisation as each participant had the same casting brief, however it also allowed for their own individual thoughts and beliefs to inspire their unique characters.

A note on Compassion Focused Therapy (CFT)

My rationale for including a character representing compassion was not only to promote *acceptance* in accordance with the IFS approach (Schwartz, 2013), it was also inspired by Paul Gilbert's Compassion Focused Therapy (CFT) model (Gilbert, 2009), which I have also experienced the benefits of therapeutically. Gilbert (2009) proposes that we have three main emotional regulation systems which interact with each other: the Threat and Protection system which alerts us to danger, the Drive system which is motivated by incentive and seeking resources, and the Contentment and Safety system (Depue and Morrone-Strupinsky, 2005). Gilbert (2009) proposes we can train the mind to be more compassion-focused, which can bring balance to the threat system and the drive system.

In the context of this study, Character 1 who represents the discomfort of public speaking, also represents the Threat system; the Protagonist, who is confident at public speaking represents the Drive system, and Compassion, who embodies unconditional acceptance, represents the Contentment and Safety system. Furthermore, Gilbert (2009) recommends mindful breathing and relaxation as way to engage with the Contentment and Safety system. As such, I incorporated breathwork and guided relaxation at the beginning of each session to help participants engage with their Contentment and Safety System.

The following chapters will explain the IFS-inspired creative character exercises in further detail. The exercises described in the following chapters took place in participants' private 'Inner Stage' of Positivity'. This internal space was constructed during session one using a guided visualisation exercise I created to encourage participants to use their imagination to create their 'Inner Stage.' This liminal space in consciousness became the venue for all subsequent sessions. Further information on this process can be found in Chapter 3, page 40.

2.3.1: Identify & Separate

The initial task of *identifying* and *separating* the parts was an integral step in increasing participants' self-awareness. Instead of viewing themselves through the singular lens of 'someone who doesn't like public speaking', they were introduced to the idea that only part of them felt this way which opened the possibility that other parts of them may also enjoy it and feel confident.

Becoming a mindful observer of our limiting beliefs or fearful thoughts can help create some distance, so that we are no longer enmeshed with them (Schwartz, 2013); this separation from our thoughts enables us to view ourselves more objectively and can lead to greater self-awareness and the realisation that we can take positive action to change our thoughts (Schwartz, 1995). With this sentiment, I created a Character Creation exercise called 'Meet the Cast.' My intention was that asking participants to create characters using their own lived experiences would help them begin to *identify* and *separate* their own beliefs about it public speaking, resulting in increased self-awareness.

Each participant was thus invited to create three characters using their own lived experience as inspiration; 'Character 1' who represented being uncomfortable with public speaking, 'Compassion' who represented unconditional kindness and acceptance, and the 'Protagonist' who represented confidence with public speaking.

The Narrative

Participants were given the following narrative: they would travel to their Inner Stage of Positivity where they would then create and develop a cast of three characters; 'Character 1' who disliked public speaking, character two, called 'Protagonist' who enjoyed public speaking and character three, called 'Compassion' who was unconditionally accepting and supportive. These characters would work together on their Inner Stage of Positivity to develop the skills and tools needed to speak confidently in public. At the end of the process, they would perform a Final Scene, in which they would participate in an Episodic Simulation of a public speaking scenario relative to their individual circumstance.

Creative Character Exercise – 'Meet the Cast'

Character 1 (C1)

C1 is the character who is most uncomfortable with the idea of speaking publicly. Drawing on inspiration from the IFS approach, this character represents an "Exile" part, which is often born out of uncomfortable or painful experiences (Schwartz, 2013). Using their own lived experiences, participants were asked to imagine what made C1 uncomfortable with public speaking.

In the context of the CFT Model, C1 also represents the Threat and Protection system, our innate flight or fight mechanism, which is characterised by anxiety, anger and sometimes disgust; a person who finds public speaking anxiety-inducing will experience their Threat System activated (Gilbert, 2009).

This character can also be viewed through the theoretical lens of Stone and Stone (1994) who argued that we each have an internal self-critical dialogue called the 'Inner Critic' which can create emotional distress and anxiety. Stone and Stone (1994) argue that rather than try to eradicate the Inner Critic, we can work to understand its message and transform it into a healthy ally. This is consistent with Schwartz (2021) who advocates that there are 'No Bad Parts.'

Houseman (2005) used exercises during voice and acting workshops that were designed to help actors become aware of their own Inner Critic. Actors were invited to notice their internal criticism and asked whether there was any evidence in their external world to support the criticism, which more often does not exist. Houseman (2005) argues that this process helps actors create distance between themselves and the inner critic, enabling them to question the criticism rather than accept it as truth. In the context of this study, a similar process occurred when participants were encouraged to explore alternative views about public speaking through the medium of their Compassionate character and confident Protagonist character. They were also given a homework assignment whereby they were invited to recall a memory where they did feel comfortable speaking with other. The purpose of this was to remind them of tangible evidence in their life of a time where they could speak confidently.

The Protagonist

The Protagonist character enjoyed public speaking and represented confidence and a willingness to learn the skills required to perform the Final Scene in which participants would deliver a speech on their Inner Stage of Positivity, in the format of an Episodic Simulation. The Protagonist character was modelled on the Protector parts as outlined by the IFS approach, who seek to be a strong and confident leader for the other parts (Schwartz, 2013). Participants were asked to imagine what the Protagonist enjoyed about public speaking, using their own lived experiences as inspiration.

In the context of the CFT systems model, the Protagonist represented the Drive system, that motivates us towards goals and resources, and is characterised by feelings of excitement, focus and feeling energised (Gilbert, 2009). This was embodied largely during the practical exercises designed to equip Protagonist, and ultimately the participant, with practical tools that they can apply when speaking in public. For further information on this process please refer to Chapter 3, page 42.

Compassion

The character of Compassion represented unconditional acceptance and self-kindness. Gilbert (2013) describes compassion as kindness and an awareness of the suffering experienced by all living things, and a desire to alleviate that suffering. McKay and Fanning (1992) define self-compassion as embodying an essence of acceptance, understanding and forgiveness. Furthermore, Buddhist philosophy promotes compassion as being essential for wellbeing (Davidson and Harrington, 2002).

According to the IFS approach, the core 'Self' part is one of empathy and maturity (Hsieh, 2015). My intention was that by creating a character of Compassion, participants would increase their awareness of their own inner compassionate Self. This character was also modelled on the Contentment and Safety system found in the CFT approach (Gilbert, 2009).

The Contentment and Safety system is characterised by a sense of peace and comfort. When an individual is no longer in Threat mode, and they have all the required resources having previously been in Drive mode, they can then enter Contentment mode (Depue and Morrone-Strupinsky, 2005; Gilbert, 2009). The CFT approach aims to increase self-compassion as a way of developing the Contentment and Safety system. Compassion is a skill that we can learn, and we can train the mind to be more self-compassionate leading to an increased sense of soothing and safety Gilbert (2005a). There is evidence to suggest that this system is linked to oxytocin-opiate systems within the brain (Depue and Morrone-Strupinsky, 2005) thus it can be inferred that developing self-compassion can increase activity in this area, resulting in a sense of soothing and safety (Gilbert and Proctor, 2006).

In the CFT approach, guided compassionate imagery exercises are used in which individuals are asked to explore what their ideal compassionate other would look like (Gilbert, 2009). This element was included within the Character Creation exercise for Compassion and participants were invited to describe what the character of Compassion looked like. Participants were also asked to imagine what words of support Compassion would offer C1 with regards to their dislike of public speaking, thus enabling participants to generate words of support and *acceptance*.

2.3.2: Acceptance

In keeping with the IFS model, once the parts have been *identified* and *separated*, they can then be *accepted* (Schwartz, 1995). This process involves fostering self-compassion for all the different parts within us (Shadick *et al.*, 2013) and viewing the parts as an internal tribe, or family, interacting with each other much in the same way family would (Hsieh, 2015; Lester, 2017).

Participants were invited to imagine that the character of Compassion unconditionally accepted C1 and the Protagonist and were asked to reflect on how this felt. They were also asked to consider how they would feel if they gave themselves permission to make mistakes, the intention being to introduce kinder, accepting self-talk, as opposed to the harsh judgment of the self-critic.

2.2.3: Transform

According to the IFS approach, once an individual has *accepted* the different parts of themselves, they can *transform* them by working to harness the qualities of the different parts and use them in a productive way (Lester, 2017). By engaging in internal dialogue with the different parts and asking them questions about how they feel and think, we can explore alternative ways of thinking which can eventually lead to transformation (Shadick *et al.*, 2013).

My intention therefore was not to try and resolve the parts that disliked public speaking, but rather to encourage *acceptance* of them and include them as a valued part of the team with skills to contribute. As such, I constructed the narrative that C1 did not have to engage in public speaking but was instead invited to work alongside Compassion to help prepare the Protagonist to speak confidently in public. This allowed for the possibility of *transforming* their initial resistance to public speaking and being able to *identify* that even if a part of them does not feel confident (represented by C1), they are nonetheless *accepted* (represented by Compassion) and able to *transform* their perception of public speaking by acknowledging that there are other parts of them who do feel confident (represented by Protagonist).

Through the creation of C1, participants were able to explore what made them uncomfortable about public speaking. With the creation of Compassion, they were able to introduce an element of self-kindness and *acceptance* by forming compassionate and supportive dialogue. By creating the Protagonist, then working to equip it with the resources needed to confidently engage in public speaking, participants were able *transform* their view from the singular self-judgement that they were uncomfortable when speaking publicly, to the perception that there were also parts of them who could confidently engage in public speaking.

2.4: Session Components

Three integral components were part of every session: Diaphragmatic Breathing (DB), Progressive Muscle Relaxation (PMR) and Guided Visualisation (GV). The impact was twofold; the breathwork followed by the PMR helped participants to access their Safety and Contentment system (Gilbert,

2009) and at the same time provided participants with practical tools to easily apply in real-world situations.

2.4.1: Diaphragmatic Breathing

Pranayama is an ancient Sanskrit word describing type of yogic breathing which relates to the control and expansion “ayama” of life-force energy, or “prana” (Jayawardena *et al.*, 2020). Pranayama practices exist in various forms, such as forced breathing, vocal chanting, nostril breathing and abdominal breathing (Russo, Santarelli and O’Rourke, 2007) and is characterised by focused inhalation, breath retention and focused exhalation (Jerath *et al.*, 2006). It is believed that pranayama practices have the potential to reduce anxiety and have a positive impact on stress-related illnesses (Brown and Gerbarg, 2005, Jerath *et al.*, 2006)

The scientific interest in these ancient breathing practices has increased in recent years due to the rise in holistic and alternative approaches to health and wellbeing (Russo, Santarelli and O’Rourke, 2007). However, Balban *et al.*, (2023) reminds us that although breathwork has been adopted in ancient practices for centuries, there is only limited scientific research on its impact on the mind-body connection.

Breathing is both involuntary and voluntary; it is an automatic process in the body, but we can also choose to control it using conscious breathing techniques (Devine, 2016). According to Brown and Gerbarg (2005) our Sympathetic Nervous System is activated when we enter a state of ‘fight or flight’ giving us the energy required to fight or flee. Controlled breathing techniques activate the Parasympathetic nervous system which counteracts the fight or flight response and begins to reduce stress (Jerath *et al.*, 2006; Meyerholtz, 2023), bringing more oxygen into the nervous system leading to a calming effect (Miller *et al.*, 2017). This can reduce symptoms of cardiovascular, muscular, and hormonal stress (Gaynor, 1999).

Consciously controlling breathing patterns has also been shown to actively influence the functioning of the Autonomic Nervous System (Russo, Santarelli and O’Rourke, 2017) for example reducing heart rate (Rider *et al.*, 1991; Sovik, 2000) as well as influencing neuroendocrine functions such as elevated serotonin levels (Jerath *et al.*, 2006), reduced cortisol release (Ma *et al.*, 2017) alongside influencing the respiratory muscle activity (Russo, Santarelli and O’Rourke, 2017).

Diaphragmatic Breathing (DB) is a controlled breathing technique characterised by deep inhalation and exhalation, diaphragm contraction and belly expansion (Ma *et al.*, 2017) which has been shown to reduce stress (Brown and Gerbarg, 2005) increase focus and concentration (Meyerholtz, 2023)

improve cognitive function (Ma *et al.*, 2017), reduce fatigue and improve emotional regulation (Arch and Craske, 2006; Jayawardena *et al.*, 2020; Zaccara *et al.*, 2018). Jerath *et al.*, (2015) suggest that conscious breathing techniques could be effective first-line treatments for anxiety and stress as they are simple, easy to teach and cost-effective (Jayawardena *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, Meyerholtz (2023) suggests using such breathing techniques before giving a presentation to reduce the fight or flight response.

Box Breathing

In addition to Diaphragmatic Breathing, I included a Box Breathing technique in the initial session. Box Breathing techniques traditionally follow a set structure in which the participant inhales for a count of four, holds their breath for a count of four, exhales for a count of four, before holding again for a count of four (Dar, Ekart and Bernadet, 2022).

According to Devine (2016) five minutes of box breathing can foster a sense of deep calm focus and alertness which will leave an individual feeling grounded and ready to act. Box Breathing is widely used in hospital settings and its use is recommended when working with trauma experienced individuals (Malchiodi, 2020).

Morrison (2023) suggests using breathing techniques such as Box Breathing in combination with other relaxation techniques to maximise their effect before attempting challenging tasks. As such, in the initial session I combined Box Breathing with Progressive Muscle Relaxation (PMR). Standard Diaphragmatic Breathing was then used as a precursor to the PMR in subsequent sessions.

2.4.2: Progressive Muscle Relaxation

Progressive Muscle Relaxation (PMR) is a relaxation exercise which involves systematically tensing and relaxing muscle groups. This process can relieve physical tension held in the muscle, and increase relaxation (McCallie, Blum and Hood, 2006). According to Harorani *et al.*, (2020) anxious thoughts can cause muscles in the body to tense up in response; by systematically relaxing each muscle group, we can reduce anxiety.

The concept of PMR was first conceived in 1934 by Dr Edmund Jacobson who theorised that neuromuscular hypertension could lead to negative emotional states (Conrad and Roth, 2007). Jacobsen (1938) identified that the systematic tensing and subsequent release of different muscle groups, alongside focused attention on the feelings and sensations in each muscle group can foster a sense of deep relaxation (Bernstein and Borkovec, 1973; McCallie, Blum and Hood, 2006).

Torales *et al.*, (2020) argue that the exact mechanisms of PMR are not fully understood, however, its efficacy in increasing relaxation has been widely documented in clinical populations, such as those with burns injuries (Harorani *et al.*, 2020), headaches (Barrows and Jacobs, 2002), Irritable Bowel Syndrome (Heymann-Monnikes *et al.*, 2000) lung cancer (Kirca and Kutluturkan, 2021), breast cancer (Metin *et al.*, 2019), alongside non-clinical populations such as young adults and students (Dolbier and Rush, 2012; Wilczynska *et al.*, 2019) and corporate workers (Ponce *et al.*, 2008).

Originally the technique involved tensing over 30 different muscle groups (Barrows and Jacobs, 2002) however this was eventually shortened by Bernstein and Borkovic (1973) who developed the Abbreviated Progressive Muscle Relaxation (APMR) which focuses on sixteen muscle groups. A study by Dolbier and Rush (2012) explored the impact of APMR on a sample of highly stressed college students and found it to be a successful intervention which significantly reduced stress in the short term.

APMR is safe to use and requires no equipment thus making it cost-effective (Harorani *et al.*, 2020; Dolbier and Rush, 2012) simple to demonstrate and easy to learn (Liu *et al.*, 2020), and individuals do not need to receive formal training before using it as a technique (Carver and O'Malley, 2015).

Metin *et al.*, (2019) propose that using PMR in conjunction with Diaphragmatic Breathing can enhance relaxation and focus by bringing more oxygen into the muscles. Given that APMR is effective at reducing anxiety, easy to learn and compliments other approaches, it was included as an integral part of each session alongside Diaphragmatic Breathing, as a precursor to the use of Guided Imagery.

2.4.3: Guided Imagery

Headspace (2023) describe Guided Imagery (GI), (used interchangeably with Guided Visualisation) as a practice in which deliberate focus is placed on each of the body's five senses with the intention of creating positive healing messages throughout the physical body and the mind.

We can use GI to construct images in our mind that feel 'real' to our body. This mind-body connection can stimulate physiological changes, as the Guided Imagery sends a message to the centres of the brain that regulate our emotions. This can impact the endocrine system, immune system and autonomic nervous systems, resulting in physiological changes (Science Daily, 2008).

A useful way of illustrating this is to imagine cutting open a juicy lemon and eating a slice. Most individuals will notice that their salivary glands have begun to activate in anticipation of the lemon, despite the lemon being imaginary.

Mental Imagery

Before we return to the guided element of GI, let us first consider mental imagery aspect. Imagery exercises rely on an individual's ability to mentally construct a scene in their 'mind's eye' (Hassabis *et al.*, 2007; Dawes *et al.*, 2020; Zeman *et al.*, 2020) to recreate a perceptual experience (Heyes and Holmes, 2013, p.11).

This can involve Scene Construction, in which individuals mentally construct and maintain a coherent scene in their mind's eye (Hassabis and Maguire, 2009), and Event Construction, in which individuals mentally assemble the elements of the event, such as the people, places and objects (Brunette and Schacter, 2021).

According to Greenberg and Rubin (2003) visual details can serve as a cue to access sensory information from other modalities, enabling us to engage in multiple sensory modalities simultaneously, such as taste, smell and auditory information (Holmes and Mathews, 2010). It is believed that those able to generate more vivid imagery, may have a more intense sensory experience. D'Argembeau and Van der Linden (2006) found that those with stronger visual imagery were able also to experience a more enhanced sensory experience when recalling previous events and imagining future events.

Mental imagery can have a direct impact on the emotional centres in the brain that respond to sensory input and can serve as an 'emotional amplifier' in both positive and negative emotional states (Holmes and Mathews, 2010; Taylor *et al.*, 1998). According to D'Argembeau and Van der Linden (2006), participants with enhanced visual imagery felt more intense emotions when projecting themselves into future events, than those with less vivid visual imagery.

A note on Aphantasia...

It is worth highlighting that there are small numbers of the population for whom the 'mind's eye' does not exist (Clemens, 2018). Individuals with this condition, known as 'Aphantasia', experience a reduction or in some cases, a complete absence of voluntary visual imagery, when both awake and asleep (Black *et al.*, 2021). It is currently estimated that Aphantasia affects between 2% and 3.3% of the population (Clemens, 2018; Zeman *et al.*, 2020). According to Dawes *et al.*, (2020) it is through the experience of guided imagery exercises that most people discover they have aphantasia.

Although this condition is very rare, it was possible that participants in this study may discover their inability to use their mind's eye when asked to engage in guided imagery tasks. To counteract this should it arise, I followed the suggestions of Black *et al.*, (2021) who proposed emphasizing the use of other sensory modalities to help those who struggle with visual imagery to engage in the process. As

such, the guided imagery scripts incorporated all the sensory modalities. Although one participant reported finding the process of visualisation challenging, no participants reported Aphantasia.

The use of Future Focused Guided Imagery

Guided Imagery can also be used to guide behaviour related to the attainment of personal goals in the future (Conway, 2001). We know from Hassabis and Maguire (2009) that the construction of images plays a crucial part in memory recall and can also be used for planning for future events (D'Argembeau and Van der Linden, 2006).

'Episodic Simulation' is the term given to the "*construction of a mental representation of a specific autobiographical future event,*" (Brunette and Schacter, 2021, p.1). Taylor *et al.*, (1998) demonstrated that individuals can engage in mental simulation to evaluate possible outcomes and subsequent actions of future scenarios. 'Episodic Future Thinking', therefore, is the term given to the ability to imagine events that may occur in one's own future (Schacter, Benoit and Szpunar, 2017).

Effectiveness

According to Boland, Riggs and Anderson (2018), engaging in episodic simulation of future events can lead to an increase in perceived control of future circumstances and can help individuals feel more prepared for previously avoided situations due to anxiety (Landkroon *et al.*, 2022). Altgassen *et al.*, (2015) argue that the likelihood of completing a previously avoided task increases after an episodic simulation of the intended task.

Imagining a possible outcome (such as a particular candidate winning an election) may increase our belief that the imagined outcome will occur (Carroll, 1978). Thus, it follows that we can use positive episodic simulation to strengthen the belief that a positive outcome is possible. This is supported by Libby *et al.*, (2007) who argue that imagining our behaviour in the future can increase the probability of us performing that behaviour.

According to Taylor *et al.*, (1998) when we think of a set of events in our mind's eye, and imagine them in concrete form, they often appear real and true. This could be attributed to the fact that mental simulations tend to be constrained by what is possible as opposed to what is magical, and as such are useful for the anticipation of future events.

In a study involving individuals with public speaking anxiety, Landkroon *et al.*, (2022) discovered that positive mental imagery of future scenarios helped reduce both pre-event anxiety, as well as reduced anxiety during the speaking event when asked to present in a Virtual Reality (VR) environment as part of Virtual Reality Exposure Therapy (VRET). This is supported by Reeves *et al.*, (2022) who found that

VRET has been successful in reducing the symptoms of public speaking anxiety. The present study did not employ Virtual Reality technology, however there are parallels that exist between the computer-generated world of VR, and the internally generated world created by participants where they were guided through an episodic simulation of a public speaking event.

GI and Episodic Simulation in Practice

Given its documented effectiveness at increasing the likelihood of taking future action, Guided Imagery (GI) was employed as an integral component of the study. Each session built on the imagery created in the previous session and culminated in a guided Episodic Simulation of a confident public speaking experience relative to the real-life world of participants; the intention behind this was to increase the likelihood of participants feeling confident enough to engage in a similar activity in real life. Furthermore, by using GI, participants were able to create their own Inner Stage of Positivity which served as positive and compassionate space that they could access regardless of geographical location.

Context Through the Lens of Performance

As the study was partly rooted in my own experience as a performer, the exercises were created using a performance-based lens. Parallels can be drawn from the work of sociologist Erving Goffman who adopted a dramaturgical framework in *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life* (Goffman, 1959). According to Goffman (1959) the way individuals present themselves to others can be considered a performance, much like actors playing a role. This notion is supported by Schechner (1988) who suggests that performance extends beyond the theatre and into the actions of everyday life. In essence, we are all performers. Furthermore, people may seek to monitor and portray themselves the way they believe their audience would like to experience them; a process referred to by Goffman as 'Impression Management.' Integral to this theory is the suggestion that individuals have a 'front stage' persona, in which they may attempt to suppress any traits or behaviours that might be viewed as unfavourable by their audience (Goffman, 1959). Such suppressed traits are more likely to be expressed 'backstage' in an informal setting where it is safe for them to relax and disregard any front they may have adopted (Solomon *et al.*, 2013).

The present study sees participants creating the role of 'Protagonist' in much the same way as an actor rehearsing for a performance. The character development of the inner Protagonist preparing to engage in public speaking, is not unlike Goffman's theory of Impression Management; by focusing on the relevant resources, and developing a performance inspired practical toolkit, participants can

prepare to perform the role of their Protagonist on their 'front stage' in accordance with the relevant presenter traits they perceive the audience will find desirable. Those traits perceived as undesirable however, such as a lack of confidence or inability to speak loud and clear, may be evident in the creation of Character 1, who dislikes public speaking. As such, this character is more likely to remain 'backstage' and out of sight.

Insights from theorist Konstantin Stanislavski have also influenced the present study. When creating a role, Stanislavski (2013) emphasised that actors must create the given circumstances of the character by asking questions with prefixes such as who, what, when, where, why and how. These questions allow an actor to create a set of circumstances such as the history, the present context and future desires of a character. Given circumstances enable character development and establish an understanding of motivations and objectives, which can lead to a more authentic performance (Polanco and Bonfiglio, 2016).

Stanislavski's process of creating given circumstances was re-interpreted and applied during the Character Creation exercise 'Meet the Cast.' Using their own lived experiences as inspirations, participants were asked to describe who each character was, what they were wearing, what age they were, how they felt about public speaking and why they felt that way. These questions established a set of given circumstances for each character. Using their own lived experiences to help create the characters, the process of establishing the given circumstances provided a space for participants to reflect upon their own given circumstances in relation to public speaking. This process can be found in Appendix 4, page 93.

A revised version of this process was also applied during the Character Observation task in which participants were asked to observe someone they believed was an effective public speaker. They are asked to observe what their chosen subject's physical actions were, how they used their vocals, what their energy was like when presenting, how they engaged with their audience. By establishing these circumstances, participants were able to develop an awareness of the traits they believed would help them to speak confidently in public. This process can be found in chapter 2.5.3, page 30.

An integral component of the present study is the use of Guided Imagery (GI). Being able to access inner imagery is an essential component of acting (McGaw, Stilson and Clark, 2008). GI is a technique commonly employed in acting training with the intention of helping theatre actors engage with the world of the play (Black *et al.*, 2021). Describing a psychophysical approach to acting, Black *et al.*, (2021) suggest that the psychological element of the imagination, inspires the physical movement within the body; the actor visualises the imagery and experiences an emotional response which then influences their movement. Furthermore, with reference to Stanislavski's given circumstances,

Margashak (2002, p. 98) argues that actors must employ inner visual imagery in relation to the given circumstances of the character and use these images continuously when on stage; this in turn can bring depth to the role.

With these concepts in mind, and where appropriate, I explained the exercises through the lens of a performer. Not only did this provide context for participants, but it also demonstrated that performance techniques can also be successfully used by non-performers.

2.5: The Performance-Inspired Practical Toolkit

The initial research sessions were designed to address the first key aim of the study; the increase of self-awareness. This was achieved using the aforementioned Character Creation exercises intended to help participants *identify* and *separate* the parts of themselves in relation to public speaking (Schwartz, 2013). In doing so, they developed the awareness that only part of themselves disliked public speaking and that another part of themselves, their very own inner Protagonist character, held a positive perception of public speaking. Furthermore, they realised they were able to generate words of *acceptance* and support for themselves by identifying with their inner Compassion character.

A second key aim of the study was to increase participants' awareness of skills and tools that could *transform* their public speaking ability. To achieve this, participants were first asked to complete a homework assignment of a Stanislavski-inspired Character Observation task (Stanislavski, 2013) whereby they observed someone who they perceived as a confident public speaker. Their observations were then incorporated into a practical session in which they were taught some simple and effective tools.

At the beginning of the session, participants experienced a guided visualisation designed to connect them with the three characters they had created previously and were given the narrative that characters C1 and Compassion were to work as a team to equip the Protagonist with skills and resources required to speak confidently in public.

Although the exercises took place largely in participants' imaginary Inner Stage, they were encouraged to open their eyes and physically participate where possible. This was to develop practice at shifting their focus between being alert in the real world and closing their eyes to access their positive inner world. The skill of being able to readily access this positive inner world is a tool that can be used to activate the Safety and Contentment system (Gilbert, 2009).

What follows is a description of the performance-inspired tools that were incorporated into the practical session.

2.5.1: Vocal Warm-up

Raphael and Sataloff (1997) suggest that speakers must undertake the appropriate vocal preparations to appear focused and relaxed, which can reduce performance anxiety. Tedesco and Patterson (2015) explored the impact of brief vocal warm-up training and found that it reduced anxiety about speaking, whilst increasing participants' willingness to communicate, and self-perceived competence levels.

The benefits are widely accepted, despite the lack of rigorous scientific evidence (DeFatta and Sataloff, 2012; Portillo *et al.*, 2018) and include an increase in blood flow in the muscles (Elliot, Sundberg and Gramming, 1995; McHenry, Johnson and Foshea, 2008), leading to improved vocal quality (Amir, Amir and Micheali, 2005). Raphael and Sataloff (1997) recommend engaging in vocal warm-ups at least three weeks prior to delivering the speech to develop the voice to the optimum condition; this will also prepare the body to reach the correct alignment for optimum breathing. Furthermore, focusing attention on the sensations experienced during the warm-ups will increase effectiveness and aid relaxation, leading to a sense of psychological readiness to perform and improved vocal quality (Raphael and Sataloff, 1997; McHenry, Johnson and Foshea, 2009).

Participants were first guided through a fascial muscle warm-up exercise used by drama practitioners called 'Ewy Chewy Toffee' (Swale, 2017), in which they were guided to chew an imaginary toffee in order to increase blood flow to the muscles in the face, jaw and lips to help with articulation. Next, they were taught a simple vocal fold warm up, a vocal hum (Goldman and Goldman, 2007) which stimulated blood flow to the vocal folds, and the vibrations also created an internal massage which has been known to reduce stress (Miller *et al.*, 2007). Finally, participants were shown how to project their volume using a simple technique whereby they expanded the hum into the world "mah." By changing their oral posture from closed lips into an open mouth, they were able to experiment with their resonance and volume safely (Munson, 2003; Hafler, 2016).

2.5.2: Power Pose

The physical posture that humans adopt can convey non-verbal information, for example, expansive postures which are open and maximise the use of space may exude a sense of power (Carney, Hall and LeBeau, 2005; Hall, Coats and LeBeau, 2005; Carney, Cuddy and Yap, 2010; Bombari, Schmid Mast and Pulfrey, 2017). Contrastingly, contractive, closed postures that adopt minimal space may convey a sense of powerlessness.

Studies have shown that those who adopt power poses are more likely to report a feeling of power (Carney, Cuddy and Yap, 2010; Huang *et al.*, 2011). Similarly, Schubert and Koole (2009) found that male participants who adopted the gesture of making a fist were more likely to perceive themselves as assertive and powerful. According to Galinsky, Gruenfeld and Magee (2003), a feeling of power can directly lead to action whereas a feeling of powerlessness is likely to lead to inhibition (Keltner *et al.*, 2003).

A 'Power Pose' is a physical posture that when adopted, can display power (Ranehill *et al.*, 2015). A study by Carney, Cuddy and Yap (2010) caught widespread media attention when it explored the physiological impact of a 'Power Pose' on a group of 46 participants and found that Power Poses can elevate testosterone and reduce cortisol, as well as increased feelings of power. They observed an opposite pattern in participants who adopted a low-power pose. Findings demonstrate that adopting powerful physical posture can influence state of mind and positively impact physiological processes associated with power and dominance.

Ranehill *et al.*, (2015) replicated the initial study by Carney, Cuddy and Yap (2010) with a larger sample of 200 participants and found that power posing had a significant impact on self-reported feelings of power, supporting the original findings. However, they were unable to find any significant influence on testosterone levels and as such the effectiveness remains an ongoing open debate (Bailey, LeFrance and Dovidio, 2017; Cesario, Jonas and Carney, 2017; Jonas *et al.*, 2017).

Carney, Cuddy and Yap (2010) demonstrate that by simply adopting a different posture, one can prepare their psychological state and physiological system for stressful situations such as speaking in public and can foster as sense of "fake it till they make it" (Carney, Cuddy and Yap, 2010, p. 1367).

A similar study by Cuddy *et al.*, (2015) explored the impact of power poses on job interview performance. The findings demonstrated that those in the 'high' power pose (open and expansive) group performed better at the mock interview and were more likely to be selected for the job than those in the 'low' power pose group (closed and contracted). This suggests a causal relationship between non-verbal behaviours carried out as preparation, and the subsequent performance that follows.

A Popular Power-Posing Protagonist

An article by Rosenberg (2011) draws parallels with the scientific research on power poses and well-loved fictional protagonist, Superman. Reflecting on a scene in the first Superman film, she describes a moment where Clark Kent reveals his true identity to female protagonist, Lois Lane:

As Clark waits for Lois, he's hunching over, trying to appear timid and unpowerful. He has a moment when he decides to tell Lois his real identity; he stands up tall, takes his glasses off and changes the tilt of his head. His body fully assumes a position of power and it is a pleasure to watch this embodiment of power as he allows himself to take up more space.

Similarly, Dr David Hamilton (2015; 2022) also makes the link between Superheroes and power posing in his self-help book *I Heart Me*, when highlighting the findings of Carney, Cuddy and Yap (2010). Throughout my training as a Holistic Practitioner, I attended several of Dr Hamilton's talks and seminars during which he guided the audience members on how to adopt the power pose.

Having performed this several times under his direct instruction and having personally felt the benefits of it as I have stood nervously in the wings as a performer, I felt it would be a simple and effective practical tool for participants. Participants were informed that their inner Protagonist character was going to adopt a posture used by well-known superhero protagonist, Superman (Rosenberg, 2011; Hamilton, 2015; 2022). Following the recommendations by Hamilton (2015; 2022) they were instructed to stand with feet hip-width apart, with their shoulders back and head facing forward in an open expansive pose. They were then instructed to put their fists into a ball and place them on their hips (Schubert and Koole, 2009). Finally, participants were informed that holding this posture for three to five minutes would increase their feelings of power (Keller, Johnson and Harder, 2017).

2.5.3: Character Observation and Awareness of Public Speaking Skills

Prior to the practical session, participants were given a Character Observation task where they were asked to observe someone they perceived as being a confident public speaker. Observation is a common skill that is developed during actor training (Acting in London, 2023; para. 1) and has been incorporated into the teachings of well-known practitioners such as Konstantin Stanislavski (Stanislavski, 2013) and Michael Chekhov (1991), Sanford Meisner (Meisner and Longwell, 1987) and Lee Strasberg (Strasberg, 1988).

Merlin (2014) proposes that even without direct experience of a situation, we can gain an insight into what it is like through observing others having said experience, arguing that performers must find a way to identify with the character and explore how they might relate and behave similarly. As actress Meryl Streep claims, "Acting is not about being someone different. It's finding the similarity in what is apparently different, then finding myself in there" (Acting in London, 2023; para. 2).

Participants were invited to approach the task much the same as an actor who is observing in preparation for performing a role, in this context, the confident public speaker that they aspired to be. They were asked to observe and take notes on the following features:

Physicality

Participants were asked to take note of posture and body language. Clarke (2021) reminds us that performers must be aware of their physicality when on stage, as much of our message is delivered with nonverbal communication (North, 2020). Thus, performers must consider their movement, gesticulation, and facial expressions. Haydon (2017) suggests using open body language to invite connection with the audience and suggests that a straight posture will make the speaker look more in control and confident. Furthermore, Johnson (2022) suggests using open hand gestures to appear confident. Smiling is a positive facial expression that can foster connection; however, Stahl (2017) argues that the overuse of smiling can make presenters appear naïve. Stahl (2017) proposes that smiling with purpose can come across as more sincere.

Vocal Qualities

Participants were asked to notice the voice of their chosen speaker. According to Schmidt, Andrews and McCutcheon (1998) there are certain vocal attributes that can lead to inattention of the listener, such as speaking too fast or too slow, and lack of variability in pitch. Similarly, Haydon (2017) highlights the importance of vocal tone and speed. Nervous speakers often speed up when they are talking and thus must remember to speak more slowly. Haydon (2017) also suggests varying the tone of voice to avoid sounding monotonous and be prepared to exaggerate more than you would in an everyday conversation. Furthermore, performers must also be able to project their voice to fill the space they are in (Pruner, 2022).

Energy Levels

Participants were asked to take note of the energy levels portrayed by their chosen speaker. Experts at Ginger Leadership Communications (2016) suggest that speakers must keep their energy at a level higher than the audience's energy, although not over-exaggerated. Furthermore, Johnson (2022) suggests that remaining flexible and adaptive in response to the unexpected will help keep their energy calm and keep the audience engaged.

Eye Contact & Engagement

Participants were asked to observe the use of eye contact to engage with the audience. According to Johnson (2022) confidence can be demonstrated by maintaining eye contact. Looking at different sections of the audience throughout the speech, you will help speakers maintain eye contact (Haydon, 2017). Stahl (2017) recommends making direct eye contact between 30-60% of the time to maintain connection. Furthermore Jean-Pierre, Hassan and Sturge (2023) suggest holding eye contact while delivering key points of information.

Knowledgeability

Participants were asked to observe how knowledgeable their chosen speaker appeared to be. According to North (2020), preparing and becoming comfortable with the content is the best way to relieve anxiety and appear knowledgeable. Furthermore, Haydon (2017) suggests rehearsing the speech for days or weeks before the event to consolidate the knowledge of the topic.

Further Skills That Were Considered Within the Practical Session

Service to Others

North (2020) reminds us that the presentation is for the audience, not for the presenter. Participants were invited to consider that their speech may be an act of service to the others in the form of imparting wisdom and information. This sentiment can allow for a shift in focus from internal judgment of their ability to external focus on the needs of their audience.

Storytelling & Humour

Participants were invited to consider the use of storytelling as a way of delivering information. Processing systems in the brain often store information in the form of stories (Chibana, 2015; para. 21) and indeed, storytelling is one of the first forms of communication (Kaufman, 2003). Chibana (2015) recommends telling a personal story which can enhance the connection with the audience, and grab and sustain their attention (North, 2020). Furthermore, Kaufman (2003) highlights that storytelling can convince an audience more than statistics or facts.

Permission to Make Mistakes

The final resource participants were invited to consider during the practical session was the idea of giving themselves permission to make mistakes, allowing for the fact that nobody is perfect. The intention behind this was to continue developing *acceptance* as promoted within the IFS approach, and a sense of compassion as advocated by the CFT approach. North (2020) reminds us that nobody expects us to have perfect communication when delivering a speech. Participants were guided to reflect on what life might look like if they gave themselves permission to get things wrong, thus developing an alternative non-critical way of viewing their public speaking experiences.

Chapter 3: Methodology

The present study aimed to explore whether an increase in self-awareness, coupled with an awareness of relevant practical tools, could lead to a perceived increase in confidence towards public speaking. To achieve this, four person-centred interactive sessions were created, comprising of original creative exercises inspired by the Internal Family Systems (IFS) approach (Schwartz, 2013; see Chapter 2.2, p. 11), alongside relevant practical exercises.

A mixed methods approach was adopted. The study was largely qualitative in nature using ethnographic data gathered from session transcripts, homework tasks and exit interviews. This allowed me to gather highly individualised data, which facilitated the subjective and nuanced nature of the study. Furthermore, it provided a space for participants to self-reflect thus creating an environment conducive to increasing self-awareness.

Quantitative assessment tools were also used at both the beginning and end of the study to provide numerical evaluation, which enabled an objective comparative analysis. Furthermore, it provided participants with a numerical representation of the utility of the study. Findings from all sessions were collated analysed using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) to identify common themes.

There is a field of literature broadly related to a range of arts-based methods for participatory arts research (see Adams and Owens, 2021; Prior, Kossak and Fisher, 2022). The study adopted a Practice-Led Research framework in which research was conducted using live participants. This framework was selected due to the significant emphasis placed on the use of creative practice to gain new insights and understanding about ways to improve confidence in public speaking (Sullivan, 2009) as well as new knowledge about the operational elements of the practice (Candy, 2016). Therefore, use of live participants enabled me to assess the utility of the research sessions in practice as opposed to remaining purely theoretical.

By taking part, participants received notable benefits: they experienced an increase in self-awareness and self-confidence; they developed practical tools and resources to support them during public speaking activities; they learned how to use their imagination to create positive inner environment, and they were shown a tangible numerical value which provided an objective measure of their increase in confidence.

3.1: Research Methods

The fear of public speaking can be measured in various ways, such as measuring an individual's physiological response or through behavioural observation (Heimberg *et al.*, 1990; Ebrahimi *et al.*, 2019; Gallego *et al.*, 2022). However, as the nature of the study was to explore individual perceptions of their confidence levels with regards to public speaking, rather than physiological measures, self-reporting measures were used.

Self-reporting measures can be used to assess a participant's perception of their own state of anxiety towards public speaking (Ebrahimi *et al.*, 2019). According to Gallego *et al.*, (2022) assessment of public speaking anxiety commonly uses self-report measures. Interventions for social anxiety conditions, like the fear of public speaking, which are evaluated using self-reports have been shown to be more effective than those evaluated using physiological and behavioural measures (Heimberg *et al.*, 1990; Ebrahimi *et al.*, 2019).

The self-reported data was gathered using a mixed methods approach which employed quantitative assessment tools applied at the beginning and end of the study to obtain numerical measures, alongside qualitative data collection in the form of ethnographic accounts, reflective homework tasks and semi-structured interviews.

3.1.1: Qualitative Methods

Data collection was primarily qualitative, consisting of ethnographic accounts, descriptions, and reflections during homework tasks, and semi-structured interview was employed to ensure standardised topics were discussed, whilst allowing space for rich ethnographic accounts to be gathered.

Ethnography

Ethnographic inquiry can be represented in theatrical form using a Performance Ethnography approach (Bird, 2022). According to Conquergood (2003), an ethnographer may view the world as a performance and find meaning in the everyday actions of participants. These lived experiences can be used to create scripts and subsequently embodied and represented in the form of performance (Pelias, 2008), such as the Yoruba-based performance *Searching for Osun*, (Jones, 2001), or the poignant film *Still/Here* (Jones, 1997). Similarly, autoethnography involves researching the self and analysing personal experiences, which can also be presented as a performance (Spry, 2009). Where ethnography helps us

understand how others view the world around them, autoethnography can be useful in understanding how we construct our own view of the world (Spry, 2001).

Due to size constraints of this study, the ethnographic findings were not represented in the creation of a theatrical performance, nor was it possible to include any autoethnographical accounts of my own personal increase in self-awareness as a consequence of performing the multiple roles of researcher, compassionate mentor and facilitator within this study. However, if this were a larger study, the cast of characters created by participants using their own lived experiences during the 'Meet the Cast' exercise could have been used to create a performance. This may be a possible route of exploration in future studies, as well as including autoethnographical reflections of my own experiences during the research process.

Ethnography has been used to explore public speaking in various language-based contexts; for example, Karmala *et al.*, (2019) used ethnography to explore the teaching-learning process of public speaking in an English language course. Similarly, Brown (2008) explored the use of the English language amongst international students, found that many students suffered anxiety and low self-confidence when speaking English. Ethnography has also been used to explore the benefits of mindfulness, which links in with the context of this study. A meta-ethnographical study by Malpass *et al.*, (2011) which explored patients' experience of using mindfulness to reduce stress and depression, uncovered the process of how patients developed their understanding of their condition and the role of mindfulness practices in managing their condition. Similarly, Williams *et al.*, (2022) employed meta-ethnography to understand of how mindfulness practices can help patients increase their awareness of their condition and develop agency.

Ethnography is increasingly used in healthcare settings (Campbell *et al.*, 2003; Pope, 2005;) as it allows for a greater understanding of patients (Goodson and Vassar, 2011). The present study was non-clinical; however, the sessions did contain a wellbeing aspect with practical exercises designed to reduce the stress of public speaking anxiety. Furthermore, it sought to understand the experiences of those receiving the sessions to increase their confidence with public speaking.

Ethnography can lead to rich and detailed descriptions direct from the source, having been immersed in the setting (Macleod, 2016). In the context of this study, it helped me to gain a more nuanced understanding of the experiences of participants in the real world as opposed to a more formal laboratory setting (Mariampolski, 1999; LeCompte and Schensul, 2010). Furthermore, the use of ethnography enabled me to explore the experiences, values, and beliefs of participants (Ejimabo, 2015) and the recorded transcripts allowed me to present those reflections and perspectives of participants accurately (LeCompte and Schensul, 2010).

3.1.2: Quantitative Methods

Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA)

Currently, quantitative self-report measures for assessing a fear of public speaking are limited in that many of the scales available only focus on the cognitive aspects, such as the Speech Anxiety Thoughts Inventory (SATI; Cho *et al.*, 2004) or the Self-Statements during Public Speaking (SSPS; Hofmann and DiBartolo, 2000). The PRPSA assessment tool created by McCroskey (1970) however, also incorporates wider aspects such as behavioural and physiological experiences (Mortberg *et al.*, 2018). Although I was primarily interested in their perceptions about public speaking, I also wanted to provide participants with the tools to calm their physiology (such as diaphragmatic breathing and PMR), as well as their behaviour (such as vocal warm-ups and power posture). The varied content of the PRPSA was more applicable than more cognitive-based scales such as the Speech Anxiety Thoughts Inventory (SATI; Cho *et al.*, 2004) or the Self-Statements during Public Speaking (SSPS; Hofmann and DiBartolo, 2000).

A similar tool, such as the Personal Report of Confidence as a Speaker (PRCS; Paul, 1966), which is a shortened form of the original version developed by Gilkinson (1942), has been used widely to measure fear of public speaking, however its true-false response format, as opposed to a wider ranging Likert scale, may be considered a limitation (Cho *et al.*, 2004). In response to Gilkinson's (1942) method of obtaining responses in a true-false format in the PRCS, McCroskey (1970) chose to develop the 34-item PRPSA using a Likert scale format, to allow for flexibility when responding (Yaikhong and Usaha, 2012).

The PRPSA assessment tool therefore contains 34 items of anxiety-related stimuli specifically linked to public speaking, each of which are measured using a Likert scale response which ranges from *strongly disagree (1)* to *strongly agree (5)*. Once collated, valid scores should contain a numerical value between 34 and 170. The resulting scores placed participants in one of three categories: high anxiety, moderate anxiety, or low anxiety. Those who scored higher than 131 points were placed in the high anxiety category; those who scored between 98-131 point were placed in the moderate anxiety category, and those who experienced less than 98 points were placed in the low anxiety category.

Self-Report of Confidence

In addition to completing the PRPSA questionnaire, participants were also asked the following question at the beginning and end of the study to provide a numerical value for any shifts in their perceptions towards public speaking:

“On a scale of 0-10 how confident do you feel when speaking or presenting to groups of people? Please use the following scale: “0 – Not confident at all / 10 – Extremely confident.”

When selecting the Likert scale for the Self-Report of Confidence, I opted for an 11-point scale ranging from 0 (*Not confident at all*) to 10 (*Extremely confident*). Although Likert scales are often used in 4-, 5- and 6-point scales (Leung, 2011), Cummins and Gullone (2000) argue that an individual’s perceptions should not be limited to five levels of choice. Thus, to allow for greater sensitivity within individual perceptions, I chose to include a wider ranging 11-point scale.

3.2: Research Design

3.2.1: Participant Recruitment

Nine participants took part in the study (three male, six female). Participants were recruited on a first-come first-serve basis using an advert placed in an internal UWS staff bulletin as well as social media campaigns. To ensure anonymity, participants were identified using numbers 1-9. Participant five withdrew prior to the commencement of the study due to unexpected demands on their time. One further participant asked to join the study shortly after the study commenced, replacing participant five, thus the total number of participants remained at nine. All participants fully completed the study.

Participant ID	Age	Gender	Occupation
1	50	Male	Glasgow City Council Leisure Attendant
2	26	Female	Nursing Student
3	53	Female	Museum Educator
4	41	Male	Medical Laboratory Technician
5	47	Female	Market Researcher
6	40	Male	Marketing Consultant & PhD Student
7	41	Female	Actor & Hospitality Worker
8	61	Female	Newborn Baby Expert
9	45	Female	Senior Autism Practitioner

Table 3.1: Participant Demographics

Ethical Considerations

During both the recruitment phase and consent process, participants were informed that whilst the study involved self-reflection of their personal experiences about public speaking, it was not a clinical study designed for therapeutic intervention, rather it was creative in nature. Participants were also given contact details to relevant support providers should they feel the need for professional support. All participants understood this, and informed consent was given.

3.2.2: Session Structure Overview

Participants attended a total of five sessions which comprised of four interactive sessions and one reflective interview session. The interactive sessions were designed so that each session built upon the previous one. Furthermore, the sessions contained foundation components of breathwork, Progressive Muscle Relaxation, and Guided Visualisation. Sessions were held every two weeks to allow adequate time to complete homework tasks, which were completed in digital format and stored securely on the UWS OneDrive.

A hybrid approach was adopted whereby sessions were conducted both in-person and online. The initial session was conducted in person. Hine (2008) highlights the question of authenticity when using online interactions as research and argues that participants must be able to trust the ethnographer with their personal reflections. Given the personal reflective nature of the study, I felt it was important to initially meet in person to establish a platform of trust and rapport before conducting the remaining sessions online.

The remaining sessions were conducted using the online platform Zoom. As the study involved a significant time commitment, the online element made the study more accessible to participants and removed the complexities of travel arrangements. In addition, an intention of the study was to create a positive internal landscape which they could engage with during stressful public speaking situations, and which they could access in any location; attending the sessions online gave practice at accessing their 'Inner Stage of Positivity' from a location of their choice.

The diagram below provides an overview of the session structure, followed by a more detailed account of each session.

Diagram 3: Session Structure

3.2.3: Session Descriptions

Session 1: Set the Stage

The initial sessions were held in-person at The Wee Retreat venue in Glasgow. To establish a baseline level of public speaking confidence, participants completed Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA; McCroskey, 1970) questionnaire, alongside a numerical Self-report of Confidence in public speaking.

Participants then completed practical exercises. Firstly, they were shown a diaphragmatic breathing technique known as Box Breathing which instructed them to inhale for a count of four, hold their breath for a count of four, exhale for a count of four, and hold for a count of four (Dar, Ekart and Bernadet, 2022). The purpose of which was to provide a tool to regulate their breathing and calm their nervous system in times of stress. For further information Box Breathing, please refer to Chapter 2, page 21. A full description of the technique can be found in Appendix 1, page 86.

Breathing exercises were followed by a guided Abbreviated Progressive Muscle Relaxation (APMR; Bernstein and Borkovic, 1973) widely recognised in clinical settings (Turner, Calhoun and Adams, 1992),

in which participants systematically tensed and released sixteen major muscle groups. The purpose of this was to equip participants with a simple tool to foster a sense of relaxation in times of stress.

Ponce *et al.*, (2008) compared different timings of PMR; 25mins, 15mins, 7mins and 2mins. They found that all lengths of dosage resulted in significant stress reduction. Given the time constraints of my sessions, I adopted a 7min PMR process; this process was the same in all four sessions. A script, which was adapted from the Oxford Cognitive Therapy Centre Practical Guide (Kennerly, 2016), was created to ensure the PMR was standardised. For further information on Progressive Muscle Relaxation, please refer to Chapter 2, page 21. A full description of the technique can be found in Appendix 2, page 87.

According to Clarke (2022) listeners will likely engage in their imagination if they have been guided into a relaxed state. Participants therefor experienced a Guided Visualisation exercise immediately after the PMR in which they were invited to use their imagination to create to an 'Inner Stage' of positivity. The intention was to construct a positive scene in their mind's eye (Hassabis and Maguire, 2009) which would then serve as a venue for future sessions. Participants were asked to imagine approaching a theatre which they subsequently entered, and were given the narrative that it was a positive and safe space called their 'Inner Stage of Positivity' which they would re-visit in subsequent sessions. During this process they were invited to engage their five senses and were asked to notice what they saw, felt, heard, smelled, or tasted (Holmes and Mathews, 2010; Odenkirk, 2017). At the end of the Guided Visualisation, participants were guided back to the visual starting point, then back to full alert focus (Odenkirk, 2017; Varnum, 2021). As imagination is subjective for everyone (Gron, 2002), a semi-structured Guided Visualisation script was created for this task to ensure standardised elements, such as approaching and entering the theatre, whilst allowing space for participants to engage their own imagination to construct their own individual scene. To conclude the session participants, were asked to recall and describe the details of their experience, which would then be used to aid recall of their 'Inner Stage of Positivity' in subsequent sessions. For further information on the Guided Visualisation and Imagery, please refer to Chapter 2, page 22. A copy of the Guided Visualisation script can be found in Appendix 3, page 90.

Session 2: Meet the Cast

The remainder of the sessions were held online using the digital platform Zoom.

The intention of this session was to address the objective of increasing self-awareness. Participants completed a diaphragmatic breathing exercise and a guided PMR. This was followed by a Guided Visualisation in which they used their imagination to re-visit the 'Inner Stage of Positivity' that they

created in the previous session. Upon reaching their imaginary stage, participants took part in a Character Creation exercise inspired by the Internal Family Systems (IFS) approach (Schwartz, 2013) and the Compassion Focused Therapy (CFT) approach (Gilbert, 2009). This was an interactive exercise and character descriptions were recorded and subsequently transcribed for analysis.

During the Character Creation exercise, participants were invited to use their own lived experiences to create three characters that would be appearing on their Inner Stage of Positivity; 'Character One (C1)' who disliked public speaking, the 'Protagonist', who enjoyed public speaking, and 'Compassion' who was unconditionally accepting and supportive. Participants were invited to use their own lived experiences to imagine what Character One disliked about public speaking, what the Protagonist enjoyed about public speaking, and what Compassion would say to offer acceptance and support.

The intention behind creating these specific three characters was inspired the Internal Family Systems (IFS) approach (Schwartz, 2013), which suggests that we can *identify and separate* the different 'parts' of our self which are involved in a situation we find challenging, in this case public speaking.³

To ensure an element of standardisation, a semi-structured Guided Visualisation script was created which ensured all participants were given the same three broad Characters to create (C1, Protagonist and Compassion), but allowed space for individualisation in which each participant could use their own unique lived experiences and imagination to build the characters. A copy of the 'Session 2: Meet the Cast' script can be found in Appendix 4, page 93.

At the end of the session participants were given instructions to complete a homework assignment in which they were to conduct a brief observation of someone they perceived as a confident public speaker and take notes on the following elements: physicality, vocal qualities, energy levels, eye contact and engagement. Participants were informed that their observations would be incorporated into the next session.

Session 3: Character Development & Skills Awareness

The intention behind this session was to address the primary objective of increasing participants awareness of practical skills that can help them to speak confidently in public. Participants completed a diaphragmatic breathing exercise followed by a guided PMR. This was followed by a Guided Visualisation in which they used their imagination to re-visit their 'Inner Stage of Positivity.' Participants

³ For a reminder of the IFS approach, please refer to Chapter 2, page 11.

were invited to imagine that all three characters they had created in the previous section were standing on the stage. They were given the narrative that all three characters were to work together to equip their Protagonist with the practical skills and resources needed to speak confidently in public.

Participants were then guided through a series of practical exercises. Although the exercises were taking part in their imagination, participants were invited to open their eyes and physically take part in the practical elements, which gave them practice at shifting their focus and attention between their inner world to their outer reality. Research shows that internal imagery can trigger the brain's emotional regulation system (Science Daily, 2008), thus the intention behind this was to develop the ability to briefly focus internally, to ground themselves during times of stress in the external world.

The session involved the following practical tasks, which were inspired by exercises often used in Performance training:

Facial Muscle Warm-up: 'Ewy Chewy Toffee'

Research demonstrates that facial muscle warm-ups can encourage blood flow, which can increase vocal quality (Amir, Amir and Micheali, 2005). Participants were instructed to unwrap an imaginary toffee sweetie, place it in their mouth and subsequently pretend to chew it animatedly, using their tongue to dislodge any "toffee" stuck to their teeth (Burnard and Murphy, 2017; Drama Toolkit, 2019). Participants were guided to imagine that it became even more chewy, thus encouraging them to explore a wide range of facial movements ensuring adequate muscle warm-up. They were also encouraged to make vocalisations during the exercise as a way of connecting the sound of the voice to the vocal articulators in the mouth (Burnard and Murphy, 2017; Swale, 2017).

Vocal Warm-up: Humming and Projection

Vocal preparations can foster a sense of readiness to perform and an enhanced vocal quality (Raphael and Sataloff, 1997; McHenry, Johnson and Foshea, 2009). Participants were instructed to use a gentle toning exercise whereby they produced the sound of 'mmm,' commonly referred to as a 'hum' which was designed to increase blood flow to the vocal folds. Humming has been used as an effective technique in voice therapy for those with voice disorders, as well as those with a normal functioning voice as it is a gentle way to encourage natural voice production with minimal force applied to the vocal folds (Yiu and Ho, 2002).

Following the guidelines of Goldman and Goldman (2007) participants were instructed to gently close their lips, with teeth slightly apart (Albrecht, 2003), inhale through their nose, and create the sound /m/. According to Morrison *et al.*, (1994) a successful hum involves using a pitch that is comfortable for the participant, alongside simple phonation. Furthermore, Raphael and Sataloff (1997) suggest the most appropriate pitch is usually achieved when the correct breath support and subsequent vocal resonance has been established. As such, participants were instructed to engage in diaphragmatic breathing and instructed to close their lips and produce the sound “m” at a pitch that felt comfortable for them.

Whilst doing so, participants were mindfully guided to notice how the vibration felt on their lips, jaw, throat and sinus cavity (Verdolini *et al.*, 1998) and were informed that these areas functioned as a resonating chamber, and advised that the more resonance in their voice, the less vocal effort they will require and the more powerful their voice will be (Hafler, 2016).

The final stage of the vocal warm-up aimed to demonstrate this resonance and increase the vocal volume. Raphael and Sataloff (1997, p. 30) define projection as “maximising listener intelligibility with minimal speaker effort.” Furthermore, Raphael and Scherer (1987) suggest that speakers must modulate their vocals in accordance with the size of the room in which they are presenting, and as such, must be aware of how to project their voice without vocal injury. Participants were guided through a simple technique designed to help them project their vocals in larger spaces without maximum exertion.

Following the guidelines of Hafler (2016), participants were instructed to begin with a simple hum, followed by opening their mouth to form the word “mah”. The open vowel sound of the “ah” can project volume further than other vowel sounds such as “ee” (Fenton, 2023) due to the oral posture required to create the shape of the “ah” (Kadhim and Alassal, 2019). Participants were then encouraged to gently increase their volume by visualising the sound reaching the furthest away wall. This was repeated three times. For further information on Facial and Vocal Warm-ups, please refer to Chapter 2, page 28.

Physicality: Power Pose

Power poses are physical postures that can be adopted to display a sense of power and confidence (Ranehill *et al.*, 2015). Participants were invited to perform a ‘Superhero’ pose and were instructed to stand tall with their feet hip width apart. They were then asked to place balled fists onto their hips. Following the recommendations of Keller, Johnson and Harder (2017), participants were informed that

holding this posture for three to five minutes would increase their feelings of power. It was explained that the 'Power Pose' has been shown to have physiological effects such as increased testosterone and reduced cortisol (Carney, Cuddy and Yap, 2010). For further information on Power Poses, please refer to Chapter 2, page 28.

Reflecting on Skills Noted During Character Observation Task

Participants were next invited to reflect on what they noticed during their observations of a confident public speaker. The task was inspired by the premise that we can gain an insight into a situation through observation, despite not having direct experience of it (Merlin, 2014). As such, participants were asked what they observed in relation to the following categories: energy levels, eye contact and audience engagement. These categories were selected due to their common emergence when reviewing the background literature. Two further categories were added into the session for discussion: service to others and use of storytelling.

Finally, participants were invited to explore the idea of giving themselves permission to make mistakes and were asked to imagine what life would be like if they granted themselves this permission. The intention behind this question was to continue fostering a sense of *acceptance*. At the end of the session, participants were given the homework task of practicing the Power Pose for three to five minutes and asked to reflect on this experience. For further information on these categories, please refer to Chapter 2, page 30.

Session 4: A New Scene

Participants completed a diaphragmatic breathing exercise followed by a guided PMR, after which they were guided to their Inner Stage of Positivity for the final time. Once orientated in their stage, participants experienced an Episodic Simulation of possible future public speaking scenario relative to their individual lives. Nine separate scripts were created containing individualised public speaking scenarios, however each script contained standardised elements related to the skills discussed in the previous session, such as eye contact, physicality, vocal quality, knowledgeability, and audience engagement. A template script is located in Appendix 6, page 105. Individual scripts are located in Appendix 7a-7i, pp. 111-136.

Episodic Future Thinking refers to the ability to imagine possible future events (Schachter, Benoit and Szpunar, 2017). An Episodic Simulation therefore is a construction of a potential future scenario

(Brunette and Schachter, 2021). This technique has been shown to increase the belief in the likelihood of the imagined scenario occurring (Carroll, 1978). Participants were guided through a positive Episodic Simulation of a possible public speaking scenario that they wished to encounter in real life. Participants were invited to imagine their scenario in first-person perspective to establish a bridge between their inner imaginary world, and their external reality. The purpose was to create a positive experience of public speaking, with the intention that the Episodic Simulation would help participants view future public speaking activities more favourably, thus *transforming* their perceptions. To conclude the session, participants were given the final homework task of re-completing the PRPSA questionnaire they previously completed in the initial session.

Session 5: The Stage Door Interview

Participants attended a semi-structured exit interview in which they reflected on their experience of taking part in the study. The interviews were transcribed and analysed using Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). A list of interview questions can be found in Appendix 8, page 137.

3.3: Data Analysis

3.3.1: Quantitative Data Analysis

Scores gathered from the PRPSA questionnaire were collated into a group matrix detailing the scores before and after, alongside the difference in scores. This allowed for any shifts in scores to be easily demonstrated and quantified. The same process was applied to the scores from the self-report of confidence before and after. These tables are displayed in Chapter 4, pages 62-63.

3.3.2: Qualitative Data Analysis using Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis

All sessions were recorded except for the initial in-person session at The Wee Retreat; this was due to the main data collection for the session being in the form of the PRPSA and self-report measure of confidence. Any visual descriptions from participants of their Inner Stage of Positivity were handwritten by the researcher.

Recordings of sessions two, three, four and five were later transcribed, and participant responses were analysed using Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) which allowed for participants

experiences to be analysed in a first-person perspective (Eatough and Smith, 2017) using their own unique expression of language (Watson *et al.*, 2008).

Transcriptions and homework assignments were initially analysed individually before commencing any group-level analyses (Watson *et al.*, 2008). Individual participants responses were first categorised into broad headings: those containing reflections related to self-awareness, those containing reflections related to an awareness public speaking skills, those containing reflections related to self-confidence and those containing any other reflections. The responses were then categorised into sub-categories related to their experiences of the IFS approach inspired exercises in which they were guided to *identify, separate* the parts of them related to public speaking, and subsequently *accept* and *transform*. Responses were then collated under the aforementioned categories for group analysis of any emerging themes or patterns of convergence or divergence (Eatough and Smith, 2017).

Chapter 4: Findings & Discussion

All nine participants experienced an increase in self-awareness and an increase in confidence with regards to public speaking. To achieve this overall result, participants went through a process where they *identified, separated,* and began to foster *acceptance* of the parts of themselves through the medium of creative exercises inspired by the IFS approach, alongside developing practical skills awareness. As a result, all participants were able to *transform* their perceptions towards public speaking to various extents; this was evidenced using ethnographic accounts gathered alongside quantitative data obtained using the assessment tool Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA; McCroskey 1970), and a self-report of their confidence levels.

Participants experiences were highly individualised and subjective, due to being asked to reflect on their own personal lived experiences throughout the study. The ethnographic accounts gathered were diverse and consequently, the qualitative data was not directly comparable, however commonalities were highlighted where possible.

Due to word count limitations of this study, one participant's journey in case study format is presented, illustrating the sessions alongside key findings from other participants.

4.1: Identify & Separate

The current section displays the process of identifying and separating parts within the creative context of this study. The subsequent sections describe the acceptance process and transformation.

The findings are presented in case study format with data gathered from Participant 8, referred to as P8, alongside statements from other participants.

Case Study Overview: Participant 8 (P8)

P8 is a 61yo female, new-born baby expert who wanted to improve confidence whilst presenting on social media whilst marketing her business. During the study, P8 recalled memories related to public speaking and realised how they still impacted her today, deepening self-awareness of her own internal processing. By creating the character of Compassion, she was able to give herself support, and by engaging with her Protagonist character she gained an understanding of the relevant resources and skills. By the end of the study, P8 was able to transform her perception of her public speaking abilities.

Meet the Cast: Creating Character 1 (C1)

P8 was given the brief that she had to create Character 1 (C1) who did not like public speaking. She was invited to use her own lived experiences as inspiration to create the character.

P8: It's a girl, about 15.

Linsey: Does she look familiar?

P8: She's a version of me. Me at 15.

Linsey: How would you describe her?

P8: She's in a school uniform. This is taking back to an experience that I had when I was 15. She is wearing black flat nurse-type shoes [...] tights, a navy skirt, knee length, a white shirt. She's got a high school tie and a maroon blazer. And short hair.

In the process of creating C1, P8 recalled an early experience of public speaking at school that she found extremely stressful:

P8: It happened when I was 15 [...] I was asked to do a talk on stage at assembly. In front of probably about 200 people. [...] Before I spoke, the year head said, "and now Helen's going to speak. And as all the boys know, Helen's shy." [...] I was so embarrassed [...] looking out at everybody and just wanting the stage to have a hole where I could just disappear [...]. I just wanted off that stage. I never spoke again on the stage.

The Character Creation exercise generated an awareness that her current dislike of public speaking was rooted in her earlier experiences of feeling embarrassed whilst giving a talk at the school assembly.

Participants' experience of creating C1 was highly individualised, resulting in a varied cast of C1 characters, each with their own reasons for disliking public speaking. Although not directly comparable, an emerging commonality among participants was fear of being judged by others. This is

consistent with findings of Genard (2019) who highlighted that situations in which there may be an evaluation of speaking abilities are viewed as more stressful.

Several participants highlighted self-criticism, which is consistent with findings of Bodie (2010), suggesting that individuals with a fear of public speaking often experience ruminative thoughts of critical self-appraisal. Findings also echo that of Stone and Stone (1994) who believe that we all have an Inner Critic part of us negatively critiquing our performance.

Below are some responses from participants that highlight fears of judgement and self-criticism.

P2: "Judgement. From other people, but it could be related to judgments she's got for herself too."

P3: "He's terrified of stuttering [...] he doesn't like people laughing at him."

P4: "She' nervous about how she looks."

P5: "He thinks people will judge him and think that he's got it wrong or that he's stupid or unprepared."

P7: "He worries about not being loud enough. He's not very good at projecting."

P9: "People will think she doesn't know what she's talking about."

C1 additionally represents Threat and Protection system highlighted by Gilbert (2009), alerting us to danger and is connected to our flight or fight response. Tsousides (2017) reminds us that flight or fight response can impact our ability to speak comfortably. The descriptions below suggest that some participants experience the activation of their Threat and Protection system when thinking about public speaking activity.

P4: "She doesn't know if she's going to be loud enough, she's nervous about that."

P7: "He gets nervous and feels closed in."

P9: "Everything around her feels really big and she feels really small [...] the environment is too big, too bright."

After creating C1 and exploring what the character dislikes about public speaking, participants were asked to create a Protagonist who was confident and looking forward to public speaking. The following section highlights key findings.

Meet the Cast: Creating the Protagonist

P8 was invited to use her own lived experiences of enjoying speaking to others, as inspiration to create the Protagonist character.

When creating her Protagonist, P8 thought of the bravery and courage of her own daughter who is embracing life with a terminal illness. She also found herself thinking of the well-known public speaker and author, Gabby Bernstein:

P8: She looks like Gabby [...] she's walking across the stage confidently, back and forward, talking to everybody [...] She's wearing a white shirt, trousers and flat shoes.

Linsey: What does she enjoy about public speaking?

P8: Getting the message out and helping others. [...] They've both got incredible strengths. My daughter with her cancer and Gabby with her alcoholism. [...] I'm thinking about my daughter launching her charity after cancer. The strength and ability to stand and talk about her diagnosis in front of people, which is incredible. And very similarly, Gabby talks about how she was an alcoholic. [...] They are both very inspirational people. They help others. Ultimately they're from the heart, really, because they're trying to help people.

P8 was able to *identify* that there are parts of her that enjoy aspects of public speaking such as being able to send out a message that may be of help to others.

The exercise of creating a Protagonist character was intended to help participants *identify* aspects of public speaking that they enjoyed. In doing this, participants were able to begin *separating* from the singular opinion that they did not like public speaking to a wider perspective that only *part* of them dislikes it. Houseman (2005) suggests that in creating distance from the inner critic, represented by C1, we can question criticism rather than accept it as truth; by creating the Protagonist character and

exploring what they enjoy about public speaking, participants were able to realise that other perspectives about their public speaking abilities were available to them.

Although participant responses were individualised and not directly comparable, an emerging commonality was enjoyment of being able to share information and helping others.

P2: "Sharing information and providing knowledge and helping people."

P3: "Sharing information and knowledge. She feels excited by it because she can enthuse other people."

P6: "Sharing wisdom and knowledge to make people think."

For others it was the enjoyment of communicating with others.

P4: "He enjoys communicating [...] he feels like he belongs when he makes a connection with people."

P7: "He likes speaking to people [...] sharing stories and listening."

P9: "Being heard. That she's got to say means something."

Others enjoyed the performative nature of public speaking.

P1: "He enjoys getting a laugh from the audience."

P5: "He enjoys the theatre of it."

Gilbert (2009) argues that within our emotional regulation system lies the Drive System, which is motivated by seeking incentives and resources; the Protagonist character represents this Drive system. The findings of the study demonstrate that enjoyment of sharing information and communicating with others may be a key incentive that motivates participants to engage positively with public speaking activities.

The following section displays key highlights of participants experiences of exploring compassion and self-acceptance.

4.2: Acceptance

Meet the Cast: Creating Compassion

P8 was invited to use her own lived experiences of compassion as inspiration to create the character of Compassion.

P8: She's the most amazing fairy godmother [...] She's like you would see somebody in a pantomime [...] With a wand and a tiara on blonde hair. She's your classic good fairy. Beautiful. Fair. Her dress is pink, and it sparkles [...] I would say she's maybe 25.

Linsey: What would Compassion say to your 15-year-old self [C1], to offer her support with the challenges of public speaking?

P8: The first thing that came into my mind there was "You're loved, and you have this shining light. You can shine out when you speak." So, that's a great reassurance that you are beautiful inside, and you can let this shining light come out of you.

The space was created for P8 to generate some compassionate words of support for parts of herself that she identified as disliking public speaking. This is consistent with IFS approach ethos where all parts can be *accepted* (Schwartz, 2013) and viewed with compassion (Gilbert, 2009). The character of Compassion represented the Contentment and Safety system as described by Gilbert (2009) which is characterised by a sense of peace and comfort. By generating compassionate words of support, P8 was able to activate her Contentment and Safety system and experience a sense of comfort.

The words of compassion generated from the remaining participants were highly subjective and not directly comparable, however several participants described visually seeing their character of Compassion give C1 physical comfort such as a hug or a hand on shoulder.

P2: "She's just giving Emma a hug. A hug can be really reassuring."

P3: "She's standing right next to him with her hands on his shoulders."

P5: "I think Alan gets a lot from the hug."

P7: "She's put her hand on the side of Phil's shoulders and is saying 'You're okay, you're safe.'"

Although participants were not experiencing the physical contact directly, they experienced a sense of comfort from visualising it. This supports the research by Gilbert (2009) who promotes compassion-focused imagery as a way of accessing the Contentment and Safety system.

Other participants found comfort from supportive words they generated, which fostered a sense of acceptance and understanding, supporting Mackay and Fanning's (1992) definition of compassion.

P4: "She would say 'you just be you [...] you are awesome.'"

P5: "She's saying 'It's okay, he doesn't need to know anything else [...] you did your best.'"

P6: "He's saying 'Don't worry, you can do this. You've done it before, and I'll do it with you.'"

P9: "She's telling me it's not as scary as I think it is [...] that everyone's had to do this for the first time at some point."

To continue developing compassion and self-acceptance, participants explored the concept of making mistakes during public speaking activities. North (2020) describes how many public speakers have fears of making mistakes during a speech, reminding us that others do not expect the speaker to have perfect communication. As such, participants were later asked to consider what it would feel like to give themselves permission to make mistakes.

P8: Life would be easier. There would be less critical chatter.

P8 had the realisation that life would feel easier if she allowed herself to make mistakes. Other participants also felt the same.

P5: *"Life would be much easier. I wouldn't be second-guessing myself before I said things."*

P6: *"Life would be easier. I think I would do more and try things more readily."*

Some participants gained awareness that life could be viewed more positively.

P1: *"It would make it much better when breaking the ice with people."*

P2: *"I'd be a lot happier because I wouldn't have the constant fear of everyone judging me. I would learn to accept the fact that I am going to make mistakes."*

P4: *"Life would feel better, I would be free to be myself."*

P7: *"I would feel so much happier. I would feel more connected and have more acceptance of myself."*

Meet the Cast: P8 Summary

By participating in the Meet the Cast Character Creation exercise to create C1, the Protagonist and Compassion, P8 was able to *identify and separate* the 'parts' of herself with regards to public speaking. She developed awareness of the origins of her lack of confidence in public speaking through her creation of C1. She identified there is an inner Protagonist part of her that enjoys public speaking as it enables her to spread positive messages for others. She became aware of a source of Compassion within her and was able to begin developing a sense of self-*acceptance* by reminding herself of her inner light that she deserves to shine brightly in the world.

A full cast list of all characters are located in Appendix 9, page 139.

4.3: Self-awareness After Character Creation Exercise

During the Stage Door Exit Interview, participants were invited to reflect on their experience of the Meet the Cast Character Creation exercise and whether it led to an increase in self-awareness.

P8: The session gave me clarity about where my self-confidence has been shattered in the past when I stood in front of lots of people and they laughed. I think this is why I am more confident speaking in smaller groups.

P8 experienced an increase in awareness around the root cause of her fears. This was echoed by another participant:

P9: "There was a situation I was in a number of years ago and it felt exactly the same, I felt like that character (C1)"

Other participants described feeling as though the characters they created were part of them:

P1: "I could relate to the Compassion character because I have always said to other people 'Are you okay?'"

P3: "I think the John character (C1) is part of me because I did have a stutter at one point."

P4: "I probably go through all of those characters when I am in a room with people."

P5: "With Snape (Protagonist), I realised part of me is like that!"

P7: "All the things that I do and say were in the characters."

P9: "I've actually realised that I have got this inner large protagonist but also that I've got a protagonist, dare I say it, that needs to be kept level as well, because I have noticed that I have also got the tendency to go a little bit over [the top]."

Other participants described a shift in perspective because of the exercise:

P2: "I realised that I do have the confidence deep down and have achieved so much already."

P6: "It's opened up that there are maybe more fun ways of engaging [...] there is a new level of engagement and that is really interesting."

Although participant experiences were highly subjective, all participants experienced an increase in self-awareness after completing the Meet the Cast Character Creation exercise.

P6 reported that he found the Meet the Cast exercise challenging, and reflected that he did not fully understand the process:

P6: "I found the session hard, but I think I didn't 'get' it, I think I was expecting those characters to pop out fully formed, rather than working to create them."

A post-exercise discussion with P6 revealed that he would have preferred a more detailed outline of the exercise prior to commencement. To accommodate for this, I ensured that he was given a detailed outline at the beginning of subsequent sessions. In the final interview, he reflected:

P6: "When you explained in the next session [...] it was much easier then. [...] In the first session I was thinking "Come on Andrew, she's asking you a question!" as if he was going to answer! So, it became easier when I realised I was consciously creating it. But I enjoyed the process, I did like it."

This experience with P6 increased my awareness of individual learning styles and resultantly I became more mindful of communication skills with all participants. Future studies may include a more detailed outline of the session prior to commencing the exercises.

4.4: Transform

Once parts had been identified, separated and accepted, I explored whether it was possible to *transform* their perception of public speaking from dislike and lack of confidence to enjoyment and confidence.

Having experienced an increase in self-awareness as a consequence of the Meet the Cast Character Creation exercise, participants attended a practical session designed to develop awareness of skills that could *transform* their experience of public speaking. They were taught a combination of vocal warm-ups and physical power poses, as well as reflecting on the following resources: use of eye contact, use of physicality, varying vocal tone and pitch and energy levels and use of storytelling.

Participants gave feedback on their experience.

P8 described that she was already feeling a *transformation* in her view of public speaking:

P8: I was at a retreat the weekend before, and we had to do an introduction about ourselves, and I actually think I handled it better than I normally would. I wasn't as anxious as I would normally when I came to me talking.

Other participants reported feeling more confident.

P1: "I feel more confident with my thinking strategy [...] I realise now, if I make a mistake, just laugh,"

P2: "I do in fact have inner confidence and I am fully capable."

P3: "I felt confident knowing that if something goes wrong, it's fine."

P4: "I liked that it was a physical preparation as well as mental and emotional."

P5: "It has given me a lot of positive vibes [...] I realise I can be anything."

P7: "I felt powerful. Riled up and ready to go!"

When asked for feedback, P9 reported feeling distracted during the session, and described thinking of a scene from The Little Mermaid:

P9: "That scene sticks in my head all of the time and whenever I feel uncomfortable, and I can't speak I've got that singing in my head. [...] They are the little distraction pieces that come in every now and again. "

However, P9 later gave the following feedback about the session:

P9: "I was fully able to both understand and follow the process of the guided visualisation."

P9: "If I hadn't have taken part in this and hadn't got those techniques, I don't think I would be able to do what I have just recently done (speak at a meeting)."

Another participant found it difficult to give feedback:

P6: "The whole process I am really enjoying and finding really useful, it's actually the feedback I am finding hard [...] The imagining the scenarios [...] I can do all that, but talking about it is really difficult."

Linsey: "Do you have any idea what it is about it that feels difficult?"

P6: "I think it's just that I don't talk about myself a huge amount."

P6 gave the following feedback a few days after the session:

P6: "I found it really valuable."

Both P6 and P9 struggled to give feedback at the end of the Skills Development practical exercises, highlighting that some individuals may require a longer period of processing time before giving

feedback. Future studies may take this into account by offering longer processing time before asking for feedback.

The final step designed to foster a sense of *transformation* was an Episodic Simulation of a positive public speaking experience relative to their own personal circumstances. Nine separate guided visualisation scenarios were created, unique to each participant. Participants were invited to comment on their experience; their responses were varied due to the individualised nature of the exercise.

P8 was led through an episodic simulation of presenting live on social media, to market her business.

P8: I felt really empowered visualising my final scene I felt comfortable and happy.

Table 4.1 below displays details of the individual scenarios for each individual episodic simulation and their feedback.

Participant	Scenario	Feedback
P1	Addressing a group of walkers as their mountain guide	<i>"I felt nervous but excited."</i>
P2	Delivering a medical handover in a hospital ward	<i>"I enjoyed how the scene was made personal [...] this made the experience more relatable."</i>
P3	Delivering a workshop	<i>"Having my Protagonist in the audience when performing was very helpful."</i>
P4	Delivering a motivational speech	<i>"It was good to see the climax of the sessions and elements all coming together and seeing my confidence increasing."</i>
P5	Introducing herself to a new gardening group	<i>"It felt really real, I could imagine being there with the women in my imaginary gardening group."</i>
P6	Delivering a Ted Talk	<i>"I found it really clear and positive. I thought tweaking it to include visual references to my scenario was great."</i>

P7	Attending an acting audition	<i>"I felt we had gone full circle. I was happy and relaxed [...] I had a huge feeling of achievement."</i>
P9	Presenting at a team meeting	<i>"I can see myself being able to present this way in the future, by visualising Blur (C1), Compassion and my Protagonist sitting in front of me for support."</i>

Table 4.1: Episodic Simulation scenarios and participant feedback

Ethnographic descriptions gathered throughout the study were subjective and individualised and therefore not directly comparable. However, descriptions did demonstrate all nine participants experienced the same process: they were all able to *identify* and *separate* parts of themselves involved in their perception of public speaking. This process was facilitated by the Meet the Cast Character Creation exercise, inspired by the IFS approach (Schwartz, 2013) and the CFT approach (Gilbert, 2009), which catalysed the *transformation* from the singular perspective that they disliked and lacked confidence with public speaking, to an awareness that there are in fact parts of them that enjoyed public speaking and felt more confident. This new perspective was strengthened by development of compassion and self-*acceptance*.

Ethnographic findings were supported by quantitative data gathered using questionnaires and self-reporting measures. The following section details the quantitative data that supports the findings that participants were able to *transform* their perception of public speaking.

Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA)

Participants were asked to complete the Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA; McCroskey, 1970), to establish a baseline measure of anxiety at the thought of public speaking. Results of PRPSA questionnaires placed participants in one of three categories: high anxiety, moderate anxiety, or low anxiety. Further details of the PRPSA can be found in Chapter 3, page 37.

Participants completed the questionnaire at the end of the study to measure any changes in score. As Table 4.2 below demonstrates, 100% of participants experienced a decrease in scores, indicating a reduction in Public Speaking Anxiety. The decline in scores was variable; P9 experienced the highest reduction in score, -61 points, moving her from the high anxiety category to the low anxiety category.

The smallest reduction in score, -2 points, was experienced by P3 who began the study already in the low anxiety category, and subsequently remained there. Two participants, P4 and P7, remained in the moderate anxiety category, however both still experienced a reduction in anxiety (P4 = -16 points; P7 = -21 points).

PRPSA Scores Before and After

Scoring key: High Anxiety = >131; Moderate Anxiety = 98-131; Low Anxiety = <98

Participant	Score Before	Level of Anxiety Before	Score After	Level of Anxiety After	Total Decrease in Score
P1	138	High	121	Moderate	-17
P2	128	Moderate	91	Low	-37
P3	82	Low	80	Low	-2
P4	125	Moderate	109	Moderate	-16
P5	103	Moderate	55	Low	-48
P6	129	Moderate	88	Low	-41
P7	131	Moderate	110	Moderate	-21
P8	132	High	116	Moderate	-16
P9	139	High	78	Low	-61

Table 4.2: PRPSA Scores Before and After

Self-Report of Confidence Scale

Participants were asked at the beginning of the study to self-report how confident they felt when engaging in public speaking activities, using a numerical scale of 0-10; 0 represented not feeling confident, and 10 represented feeling extremely confident. Participants were again asked at the end of the study as a way of quantifying any shifts in self-perception of confidence that may have occurred.

Table 4.3 below demonstrates almost all participants self-reported increases in confidence, indicating their view of their confidence levels had transformed. Given the subjective nature of the study, scores varied between participants. P1 experienced the biggest shift in confidence, increasing by six points.

The lowest increase occurred for P7 with an increase in one point, however her initial self-report of confidence was already high (seven out of ten).

One participant, P3, reported a one-point decrease in confidence, however she began the study with a high score of nine out of ten. Towards the end of the study, P3 experienced a bereavement and expressed that the decrease in score was attributed to her experience of grief as opposed to losing confidence.

Self-Report of Confidence Before and After

On a scale of 0-10 how confident do you feel when speaking or presenting to groups of people? (Please circle)

0 – Not confident at all / 10 – Extremely confident

Participant	Initial Score	End Score	Difference in Score
P1	2	8	+6
P2	3	6.5	+3.5
P3	9	8	-1
P4	6	8	+2
P5	7	9	+2
P6	6	8.5	+2.5
P7	7	8	+1
P8	3	7	+4
P9	2	6	+4

Table 4.3: Self-report of confidence

4.5: Limitations and Implications for Future Study

Although the findings demonstrated that all participants experienced an increase in self-awareness, there was no baseline measurement of self-awareness taken at the beginning of the study. As such it is not possible to quantify the extent of the increase in self-awareness. Future studies may incorporate a self-awareness measurement tool at the beginning and end of the study to provide a quantitative measure to support the findings.

All participants reported an increase in self-confidence as evidenced by reflections and quantitative measures, however there was no opportunity to measure the extent of this in real life. Participants experienced an Episodic Simulation of a public speaking activity, however due size constraints and time limitations of the study, participants were not given the opportunity to subsequently perform the

public speaking activity in real life. A more extensive study could involve an additional session in which participants perform a public speaking activity they experienced during the Episodic Simulation, followed by a reflection of their experience and quantitative measuring tools. This would establish a greater measurement of the increase in self-confidence as a result of participating in the study.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

The study explored whether an increase in self-awareness alongside the development of relevant practical resources could lead to increased confidence in public speaking. To achieve this, three key objectives were fulfilled within the framework of four interactive sessions; the use of Character Creation exercises inspired by the IFS approach designed to increase self-awareness, the creation of a practical toolkit inspired by both performance theory and wellbeing techniques, and the use of episodic simulation to create a positive experience of a public speaking activity.

As a result of the study, all nine participants experienced an increase in self-awareness and subsequent increase in self-confidence to varying extents, as evidenced by participants reflections alongside the PRPSA assessment tool and a self-report of confidence.

The experiences of participants were highly subjective and variable, however the findings demonstrate that the IFS-inspired creative ‘Meet the Cast’ exercise enabled all nine participants to *identify* and *separate* the parts of themselves involved in their beliefs about public speaking and begin to foster a sense of compassionate *self-acceptance*. This experience, in combination with receiving a performance-inspired practical toolkit and participating in an Episodic Simulation of a positive public speaking experience, led participants to *transform* their perceptions of public speaking from the singular perspective of disliking it and lacking confidence, to the realisation that there were other parts of the self that also enjoyed it, and could in fact feel confident. This introduced other ways of viewing themselves in relation to the act of public speaking, which led to an increase in confidence.

A major criticism of the IFS approach is the lack of demonstrable evidence of its utility (Brownstone, Hunsinker and Greene, 2024; Earleywine *et al.*, 2024); the present study addressed this deficiency by demonstrating that the key principles of the IFS model, *identify*, *separate*, *accept* and *transform* (Schwartz, 2013), can in fact be applied within a creative context, to effectively increase self-awareness and confidence in the context of public speaking. The findings therefore contribute to a growing body of evidence that provides support of the utility of the IFS model, particularly when applied creatively alongside performance theory and wellbeing tools.

As well as being given the space to self-reflect, further utility for participants included the development of a practical toolkit to support themselves when speaking, including how to use performance techniques inspired by the theories of Stanislavski (2013) and Goffman (1959), the creation of an Inner Stage which served as accessible positive internal environment, and an understanding of how wellbeing techniques such as diaphragmatic breathing and PMR can help them self-regulate whilst public speaking. Participants also received a numerical value of the success of their

participation as demonstrated by their final PRPSA score and Self-report of Confidence score, which provided an objective measure of their increase in confidence after taking part in the study.

The insights gained in the present study may provide a springboard for a larger study of further ways in which the IFS model can be applied creatively to increase self-awareness and confidence. The present study was conducted in private individual session format, however there is scope to convert to a group workshop format which may allow the IFS model to be applied creatively with larger numbers of participants. As such, future studies could involve the development of a creative workshop that can be delivered to larger groups across various professional and organisational contexts where public speaking activities are integral to the role of participants.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Box Breathing Technique Script

We can use our wonderful breath, that is so freely available to us without condition, to bring a sense of calm in times of anxiety. I am going to equip you with a simple breathing tool that you can use in times of stress, anywhere, at any time. This calming tool is called 'Box Breathing'

In just a moment I will explain to you how Box Breathing works and then we will practice together.

First, you will breathe in through your nose while counting to 4 slowly.

Then you will hold your breath while counting slowly to 4.

You will then begin to slowly exhale for the count of 4.

Finally, you will hold your breath while slowly counting to four.

Then we will repeat a few times.

So, let's have a practice.

Breathe in through your nose, 2, 3, 4. Hold, 2, 3, 4.

Breathe out, 2, 3, 4. Hold, 2, 3, 4.

Repeat x 3

And now allow your breathing to gently return to normal, breathing in slowly, and out slowly, safe in the knowledge that you have learned a simple yet powerful way to work with your breath to bring about a sense of calm.

Appendix 2: Breathing and PMR Script

The following script was created using adaptations of multiple sources, the references of which can be found at the bottom of this page.

The script was used at the beginning of each session as a precursor to all guided visualisations.

Take a moment now to find a comfortable, well supported position, and let your body grow heavy. Close your eyes, and don't worry if they flicker, this is quite usual. Don't worry if random thoughts enter your mind, this is also quite usual. Just let them go and then re-focus on relaxing.

As you feel your body becoming comfortable, turn your attention now to your breathing, safe in the knowledge that this breath is always available to you, at any time without condition.

Safe in the knowledge that this breath, so freely given to you, can be used to bring about a feeling of calm.

Take a slow, deep breath in through your **nose, 2, 3, 4...** and out through your **nose, 2, 3, 4.**

In, 2, 3, 4, out, 2, 3, 4.

And repeat.

Notice your breathing. Where does the air go once it is inside your body? Is the air coming into your chest? Or is it coming down into your abdomen?

In, 2, 3, 4, out, 2, 3, 4.

When you breathe deeply, the air travels deep into your lungs, all the way down to the abdomen. Imagine the air pushing out your belly like a balloon on the in breath.... And deflating on the out breath.

In, 2, 3, 4, out, 2, 3, 4 (Repeat).

Notice your current level of comfort... you can adjust your position if you like.

As you begin to relax Continue to breathe in slowly and deeply ... and out slowly imagining yourself becoming heavier and heavier, sinking into the bed/chair.

Keep breathing rhythmically and feel a sense of relief and of letting go

When images drift into your mind, don't fight them ... Just acknowledge them and let them pass ...

You are a bystander: interested but not involved... Now, let us bring our focus to the muscles of your body ...

Think of your feet ... Let your feet go limp and floppy ... Feel the tension draining away from your feet ... Let your feet roll outwards and grow heavier and heavier ... Imagine that they are so heavy that they are sinking into the floor ... More and more relaxed ...

Now, think about your calves ... As you feel supported by the bed/floor beneath you, let your legs go floppy and heavy ... Feel the tension leaving your legs, draining away from your calves ... Leaving your calves feeling heavy ... Draining away from your feet ... Leaving them feeling heavy and limp ... Imagine that your legs and feet are so heavy that they are sinking into the floor... Growing more and more heavy and relaxed.

Think about your thigh muscles ... Feel the tension draining away from your legs ... They feel limp and heavy ... Your thighs feel heavy ... Imagine the tension draining away ... Leaving your legs ... Leaving them feeling limp and relaxed ... Leaving them feeling so heavy that they are sinking into the floor (or your chair) ... Let the feelings of relaxation spread up from your feet ... Up through your legs ... Relaxing your hips and lower back ...

Now relax the muscles of your hips, and lower back ... If you feel tension, let it go ... Let your muscles relax ... Feel your spine supported ... Feel the muscles relax... More and more relaxedYour hips are relaxed ... Your legs are relaxed ... Your feet are heavy ... Tension is draining away from your body...

Relax your stomach and chest muscles ... As you breathe out, let go of your tension ... Feel your stomach muscles relax ... Feel the tightness leave your chest ... As you breathe evenly and calmly, your chest and stomach should gently rise and fall ... Allow your breathing to become rhythmic and relaxed ...

Now think about your hands and arms ... imagine the tension draining away from your arms ... Leaving your upper arms ... Leaving your forearms ... Draining away from your hands ...Your arms feel heavy and floppy ... Your arms feel limp and relaxed.

Think about the muscles in your shoulders ... Now relax ... Let your head drop forward ... Let your shoulders drop ... Let them drop even further ... Feel the tension easing away from your neck and shoulders ... Feel your muscles relaxing more and more deeply ... Your neck is limp and your shoulders feel heavy ... heavy and heavier...

Think about your face muscles ... Focus on the muscles running across your forehead ... Relax your forehead and drop your jaw ... Feel the strain easing ... Feel the tension draining away from your

face ... Your forehead feels smooth and relaxed ... Your jaw is heavy and loose ... Imagine the tension leaving your face ... Leaving your neck ... Draining away from your shoulders ... Your head, neck, and shoulders feel heavy and relaxed ... heavy and relaxed.

Think of your whole body now ... Your entire body feels heavy and relaxed ... notice whether there are any areas of your body that still feel tense... You can tense these muscles tightly... and then release them... Imagine the tension flowing out of your body ... Listen to the sound of your calm, even breathing ... Your arms, legs and head feel pleasantly heavy ... Too heavy to move ... You may feel as though you are floating ... Let it happen ... It is part of being relaxed ...

Take a few moments to enjoy the feelings of relaxation and calm knowing that this feeling is always available to you, and you have the power to tap into this feeling any time you wish...

The above script was constructed using samples from the following resources:

Institute for Restorative Practices (No Date) 'Focus Family Resiliency Training Manual. Appendix B: Calming and grounding activities.' www.iirp.edu. Available at:
https://www.iirp.edu/images/conf_downloads/UmqxBC_breathinig_and_guided_visualization.pdf
(Accessed: 23rd January 2023).

Kennerley, H. (2016) *Relaxation Scripts*. OCTD Practical Guides. Available at: www.octc.co.uk
(Accessed 23rd January 2023).

Appendix 3: Session 1 'Set the Stage' Guided Visualisation

As you lie there comfortably, we are about to go on a journey to a magical stage that lives within your imagination... as we explore your unique private stage today, we do so in the knowledge that we will return to this stage in each session as we continue your journey towards that feeling of confidence when speaking with others.

From time to time your thoughts may drift and distract you... that is quite normal, don't worry. Just gently bring your focus back to your breathing as we continue on our journey...

Sometimes I will ask you questions. It is up to whether you answer aloud or internally...

As you continue to relax, you become aware that you are standing on a pathway, and up ahead you can see or sense a theatre. Take a few moments to really look at this theatre...what do you see or sense? notice it's strong, bold presence...

As you stand there gazing at the theatre up ahead, you notice that the entire building is surrounded by a sparkling golden light, magical and inviting.

You look down at your feet...

And notice that in front of you lies a pathway of 5 beautiful ornate **steppingstones** leading you towards the theatre.

As you feel your foot touch the **first steppingstone**, a wave of peace and tranquillity passes through your entire body.

You step onto the **next steppingstone**, moving closer to the theatre, you are feeling a sense of calm.

Reaching the **third steppingstone**, you feel a deeper sense of relaxation which spreads through your entire body as you step on **the fourth stone**, moving ever closer to the magical golden theatre.

And now, as you reach the **fifth and final steppingstone**, you arrive at the doorway to the theatre noticing that you too, become bathed in a beautiful golden light. Feeling safe and relaxed, you are ready to enter this magical theatre.

Enter the Auditorium

As you open the door and step inside, you become aware of an auditorium with a beautiful stage, bathed in the same inviting golden light.

This is your auditorium of positivity... this is your beautiful stage of strength and confidence...

Take a few moments to look around this magical place... imagine what it looks like... what do you notice about this special place?

Perhaps the auditorium is large.... Or perhaps it is small and intimate...

What **colours** can you see?

Notice any **smells** that fill your nostrils as you take a deep breath, breathing in this wonderful, magical space of confidence.

You walk down the aisle and sit in one of the seats, and look at your stage... notice where you are sitting... perhaps you are in the stalls... or perhaps you are in the upper circle...

Take a few moments to notice the seat you are sitting on... notice the colours and **textures** of the fabric... notice if there are any **scents**...

You continue to gaze around this magnificent theatre, perhaps there is an ornate ceiling... or perhaps you sense that it is an open-air theatre under a brightly lit star-filled sky...

Inner Stage of Positivity

You now bring your attention to the stage in front of you that is bathed in beautiful golden sparkly light... notice what it looks like... and whether there is anything on your stage... notice where the lights are placed... perhaps it is brightly illuminated... or perhaps there is a single spotlight...

This is your Inner Stage of Positivity, a place of confidence, a place of your creation where you are respected, valued and where you feel relaxed, confident, and safe...

You now find yourself approaching the stage... you slowly walk on... notice what is underfoot? Perhaps it is the classic well-treaded boards, or perhaps your stage is covered in grass... it can be whatever you want it to be because this is your own creation... your private place of safety.

Notice whether there is any scenery or props... knowing this magical stage can look however you want it to look...

Have a walk around your stage... take in the sights, the sounds, the warm glow of the lights... spend a moment basking in this beautiful space of your creation... this private, safe inner world that you can access whenever you chose....

As you face out towards the auditorium you notice or sense a little ball of light in every seat... each ball of light is filled with unconditional love and is radiating positivity towards you... supporting you as you stand confidently on your beautiful stage...

Notice how pleasant it feels to be supported...

As we prepare to leave your beautiful stage for the time being, you take one final look around and this magnificent, loving stage and auditorium, safe in the knowledge that you can return at any time you wish, and setting the intention that that you will indeed be back to visit soon to continue our work towards confidence.

Return

As you walk up the aisle towards the door, you thank this magical space for its love and positivity, and you thank yourself for creating such a wonderful positive, safe space to retreat to.

Closing the door behind you, you once again find yourself at the 5 ornate steppingstones. As I count with each steppingstone, you begin to return into the room.

Five: beginning to feel more alert...bring your awareness back to your breathing.

Four: noticing the feel of the bed/chair beneath you.

Three: gently start moving again ...wiggling your fingers and toes and having a little stretch.

Two: you are now fully aware of room that you are in.

One: eyes open, feeling relaxed and alert.

Appendix 4: Session 2 'Meet the Cast' Guided Visualisation

You continue to become more relaxed as we prepare now to visit your private, magical Inner Stage of Positivity, knowing that as we do so today, we will be continuing your journey towards feeling more confident when speaking or presenting to others.

And as we work together today with your rich and fertile imagination, I will be asking you some questions, and today you will answer those questions out loud as we work together as a cast and company, safe in the knowledge that I am guiding you through the process.

From time to time your thoughts may drift off and distract you... that is quite normal, don't worry. Just gently bring your focus back to your breathing and the sound of my voice.

And don't worry if you cannot see or sense anything, that is perfectly okay too, for it is your conscious intention to have the experience that matters the most.

So, relax and trust that your imagination will guide you.

As you continue to relax, you become aware that you are standing on a pathway, and up ahead you can once again see or sense your theatre.

Notice whether your theatre still looks the same with its:

[Individual descriptions recorded during session one were narrated here].

Or perhaps your theatre has changed shape, size, or colour. There is no right or wrong, it can look however you want it to look because it is your unique and private place of safety.

As you stand there gazing at the theatre up ahead, you notice that the entire building is once again surrounded by a sparkling golden light, magical and inviting.

You look down at your feet...

And notice once again that in front of you lies a pathway of 5 beautiful ornate **steppingstones** leading you towards the theatre. Perhaps you recognise them as the same ones as before, or perhaps today they look or feel different. They can look however you want them to look.

As you feel your foot touch the **first steppingstone**, a wave of peace and tranquillity passes through your entire body.

You step onto the **next steppingstone**, moving closer to the theatre, you feel a sense of calm.

Reaching the **third steppingstone**, you feel a deeper sense of relaxation which spreads through your entire body as you step on **the fourth stone**, moving ever closer to the magical golden theatre.

And now, as you reach the **fifth and final steppingstone**, you arrive at the doorway to your theatre, noticing that you too, become bathed in a beautiful golden light. Feeling safe and relaxed, you are ready to enter this magical theatre.

As you open the door and step inside, you step inside your auditorium of positivity... notice whether you recognise it as the same space as before, with:

[Individual descriptions recorded during session one were narrated here].

Or perhaps today it looks different.... As you look around this magnificent space, notice whether there is anything different about your stage today... knowing that your stage of strength and confidence can look however you want it to look, for it is a place of your unique, private creation.

Meet the Cast

You walk now onto the stage. As you gaze around your stage and auditorium, you breath in this magical space of your creation where we are going to continue your journey towards increasing confidence when speaking with others.

As with any theatre production, it is the cast of performers that bring the stage to life. In just a moment we are going to meet a very special cast of characters. Although the characters are different and unique, they each share a common objective; they all want to feel confident when speaking or presenting to others.

Many actors use Method Acting techniques, where they recall their own similar life experiences and then use these experiences to help them create the character that they are playing.

As you meet each character on your stage today, you are going to use your own life experiences to create each character and really imagine what each character is like. I will guide you through each step, asking you questions as we go, and I invite you to answer these questions out loud as we work through this creative exercise together.

And don't worry if you don't know the answer, just allow your imagination to help you guess, safe in the knowledge that there is no right or wrong answer, and no right or wrong way to have this experience.

Create Character 1 (C1)

You turn your attention to your stage and notice that the first cast member has stepped onto the stage. This cast member plays the role of someone who is very nervous about presenting in front of others.

Notice where are they positioned on the stage?

Are they male or female? Or perhaps they are not even human at all?

Do you recognise them? Are they familiar?

What age do they look?

Can you describe their physical appearance?

Are they wearing a costume?

Do they have any props?

You smile warmly at them and ask them their name:

[Name of C1 was recorded here]

When an actor is building a character that they will eventually perform, they must understand who the character is, and how they would think, feel and act, and *why* the character would act in such ways. And they have to imagine what it would be like to be in the characters shoes.

To help us understand this character, we are going to ask them some questions – and you will use your own experiences and your own creative imagination to really imagine what their response would be.

So you turn now to _____ and ask them:

What makes them so uncomfortable about speaking or presenting to others?

[Participant responses were recorded here].

Create Compassion

You thank them for their willingness to be open and honest, and you notice that the next cast member is about to enter the stage: this character is called Compassion and is filled with unconditional kindness and positive regard for all.

Compassion knows [Insert name of C1] inside out and has been with them their entire life supporting them, even in those times when [Insert name of C1] has really struggled with life, Compassion has been there deep inside.

You notice Compassion enter the stage and move towards [Insert name of C1]. As you observe Compassion, what do you notice?

Are they male or female?

Do you recognise them? Are they familiar?

What age do they look?

Can you describe their physical appearance?

Are they wearing a costume?

Do they have any props?

[Participant responses were recorded here].

Compassion embraces [Insert name of C1] with kindness and deep empathy, acknowledging how hard it can be sometimes for [Insert name of C1] to feel confident when speaking or present to others.

Using your own experiences of being supportive and compassionate to others, or recalling a time when you have received compassion and support from someone else, really imagine now **what Compassion would say to [Insert name of C1] if they were offering comfort and support about those challenges with speaking with others:**

[Participant responses were recorded here].

Compassion knows and unconditionally accepts all there is to know about [Insert name of C1], and this includes all their gifts, skills and qualities and abilities.

And so, if Compassion was to remind them of a situation or experience where they did feel confident, relaxed and strong, what would it be? And if you can't think of one from your own experiences, then use your imagination.

[Participant responses were recorded here].

What does Compassion see when they look at [Insert name of C1] through the eyes of unconditional acceptance and positive regard as they support them on the journey towards building confidence when speaking with others?

[Participant responses were recorded here].

Protagonist

We prepare now to meet our final cast member who is patiently waiting in the wings. Just as every play or movie has its own hero Protagonist character, we too are about to meet yours, setting the intention to work more in depth with this character in future sessions. Your Protagonist is the character who feels the most confident and strong when speaking or presenting to others.

You see the Protagonist enter the stage and approach [Insert name of C1] and Compassion. What do you notice about this character?

Are they male or female?

Do you recognise them? Are they familiar?

What age do they look?

Can you describe their physical appearance?

Are they wearing a costume?

Do they have any props?

[Participant responses were recorded here].

You ask them, what do they enjoy about speaking or presenting to others?

[Participant responses were recorded here].

The Protagonist character announces that they have been tasked to perform a scene in which they will present to a group. The Protagonist is looking forward to the task, however they are requesting the help and resources from [Insert name of C1] and Compassion to really prepare them for this final scene.

Compassion happily agrees to support the Protagonist and will be working alongside them over the next few sessions to help prepare them for the task.

The Protagonist turns to [Insert name of C1] and acknowledges how challenging it is for them when speaking or presenting to others, however they see that [Insert name of C1] has so many valuable skills and resources that could really help prepare the Protagonist for their end scene.

Compassion and the Protagonist smile warmly at [Insert name of C1] and thank them for their courageous honesty, bravery and wisdom and their valuable contribution to the work that has been done here today.

Return

As you prepare to leave your stage for the time being, you thank _____, Compassion and the Protagonist for working with you today and let them know that you will be back very soon to continue working together as a cast.

As you walk up the aisle towards the door, you thank this magical space for its love and positivity, and you thank yourself for creating such a wonderful positive, safe space to retreat to.

Closing the door behind you, you once again find yourself at the 5 ornate steppingstones. As I count with each steppingstone, you begin to return into the room.

Five: beginning to feel more alert...bring your awareness back to your breathing.

Four: noticing the feel of the bed/chair beneath you.

Three: gently start moving again ...wiggling your fingers and toes and having a little stretch.

Two: you are now fully aware of room that you are in.

One: eyes open, feeling relaxed and alert.”

Appendix 5: Session 3 'Character Development & Skills Awareness' Guided Visualisation

As you sit there comfortably, we will prepare now to visit your private, magical Inner Stage of Positivity, knowing that as we do so today, we will continue to embrace the growing feeling of confidence when speaking or presenting to groups.

As we work together today, we will continue to draw inspiration from your real lived experiences, comingled with your rich and fertile imagination, and we do so safe in the knowledge that there is no right or wrong way to have this experience.

And as we work together today with your rich and fertile imagination, I will be asking you some questions, and today you will answer those questions out loud as we work together as a cast and company, safe in the knowledge that I am guiding you through the process.

From time to time your thoughts may drift off and distract you... that is quite normal, don't worry. Just gently bring your focus back to your breathing and the sound of my voice.

And don't worry if you cannot see or sense anything, that is perfectly okay too, for it is your conscious intention to have the experience that matters the most.

So, relax and trust that your imagination will guide you.

As you continue to relax, you become aware that you are standing on a pathway, and up ahead you can once again see or sense your theatre.

Notice whether your theatre still looks the same with its:

[Individual descriptions recorded during session one were narrated here].

Or perhaps your theatre has changed shape, size, or colour. There is no right or wrong, it can look however you want it to look because it is your unique and private place of safety.

As you stand there gazing at the theatre up ahead, you notice that the entire building is once again surrounded by a sparkling golden light, magical and inviting.

You look down at your feet...

And notice those now-familiar steppingstones that lead you towards your theatre.

As you feel your foot touch the **first steppingstone**, a wave of peace and tranquillity passes through your entire body.

You step onto the **next steppingstone**, moving closer to the theatre, you feel a sense of calm.

Reaching the **third steppingstone**, you feel a deeper sense of relaxation which spreads through your entire body as you step on **the fourth stone**, moving ever closer to the magical golden theatre. And now, as you reach the **fifth and final steppingstone**, you arrive at the doorway to your theatre, noticing that you too, become bathed in a beautiful golden light. Feeling safe and relaxed, you are ready to enter this magical theatre.

As you open the door and step inside your auditorium of positivity... you take a moment now to fully notice the space with its:

[Individual descriptions recorded during session one were narrated here].

As you look around this magnificent space... know that the work we do here today will expand your ever-growing confidence when speaking or presenting to groups.

Welcome Cast

You turn your attention now to the centre of your stage and notice that your unique and wonderful cast of characters are waiting there to greet you. You greet:

Character 1 (C1)	[Individual descriptions recorded during session two were narrated here].
Compassion	[Individual descriptions recorded during session two were narrated here].
Protagonist	[Individual descriptions recorded during session two were narrated here].

You thank the group for returning to the stage today, especially [Insert name of C1] who has been courageous enough to join forces and share their skills and resources, despite being out of his/her comfort zone.

You explain to the group that today you will all be working as team to prepare the Protagonist to deliver a Final Scene in which they will present on their Inner Stage of Positivity in Session Four.

You first check in with [Insert name of C1] and ask **how they are feeling about being here today?**

Is there anything that [Insert name of C1] **needs from Compassion or the Protagonist in this moment to be able to continue with the task?**

[Participant responses recorded here].

You then turn your attention to Compassion, who is very proud of [Insert name of C1] and your Protagonist for working together today. Compassion announces that she is here to offer support to both characters today. **What does Compassion say to both characters to support them in this moment?**

[Participant responses recorded here].

Finally, you turn to your Protagonist who is very much looking forward to preparing for their Final Scene where they present to your auditorium of positivity. They are looking forward to:

[Responses given during session two were narrated here].

The Preparation

We are now going to prepare the Protagonist for their Final Scene which they will present to your auditorium of positivity.

We know now that when an actor is rehearsing for a theatre production, they must create and build the character that they wish to portray. There is however another vital part of the rehearsal process and that is taking instruction from the Director on how to perform the scene. The Director in a theatre production decides how the performance should be portrayed and guides the performers during the rehearsal process.

You now turn to [Insert name of C1] and Compassion and explain that in this task, they will have the very important role of Directors, and together they will be working with your Protagonist ensuring they have all the resources they need to perform their Final Scene in Session Four.

[Insert name of C1] and Compassion have been chosen for this task because they have all the skills, knowledge and understanding of what it takes to be a confident speaker or presenter and are able

to offer unconditional support and positive regard. And even though [Insert name of C1] has felt uncomfortable about speaking or presenting to groups, they are still excellent communicators across many different situations.

You notice that 2 chairs have appeared on stage, one for each of the directors.

[Insert name of C1] and Compassion now settle into the chairs. You notice that there is large golden circle on the floor of the stage, shimmering and radiating strength and positivity. [Insert name of C1] and Compassion have directed the Protagonist to stand in the centre of the radiant golden circle, where they will remain throughout the rehearsal.

As the Protagonist stands in the golden circle, you notice that they too are covered in golden shimmering light, radiating and luminous. And as they stand there ready to build their resources to prepare them for the Final Scene, you notice that Director [Insert name of C1] has given their first instruction, and that is to bring all their focus and awareness to their voice and the power that it holds.

Resource of the voice

Any actor preparing for a performance must warm up their voice and facial muscles beforehand, so that they can speak loud and clear. So, first off, we are going to gently warm up the Protagonists facial muscles and I invite you to join in alongside the Protagonist and you can open your eyes for this if you wish.

You notice that the Protagonist has an imaginary **toffee sweetie** in their hand. They are directed to put the toffee in their mouth and begin to chew it. But as they chew it, they notice it is getting even more chewy! In fact, it's sticking to their teeth, so now they are having to use their tongue to dislodge the sticky chewy toffee.

Now that they have the blood flowing to the muscles in their face, it's time to bring that blood flow to their vocal chords to start warming up the voice. There are many different types of vocal warm up, often involving a lot of volume, however sometimes we are in a situation where we don't have the privacy to make a lot of noise, and so a quick and simple way to still warm up your voice without much volume is **to hum**.

Simple humming can not only increase the blood flow to the vocal chords, but it can also lower our blood pressure and heartrate, and can bring us into a state of calm. Not only that, it can also stimulate the release of feel-good endorphins and oxytocin which some refer to as the "trust" hormone, allowing us to trust in ourselves and our capabilities as well as our trust in those we are communicating with. Humming quietly to ourselves in times of stress can also help us connect with our own inner Compassion character.

So as the Protagonist begins to hum, I invite you to join in too. You can vary the pitch and tone if you like but there are no notes, no rules, no set way of doing it, just allow the hum to flow.

[HUM]

As you continue to hum, take a moment to feel the vibrations of your vocal chords, and notice how the hum feels on your face. Know that by taking this simple action, you are preparing your voice to reach the volume you desire it to have when speaking with others.

And if you are somewhere where you can make a bit of noise, you can turn the hum into the word “MAH” and allow the volume to increase as your mouth forms the “AH” sound. Like this:

[MAH].

And as you create these sounds with your voice, I would invite you to once again close your eyes, and I want you to focus now for a moment on how unique and wonderful your voice is, knowing that there is only one you in this entire universe. You are the only person in the universe who gets to speak with your voice, and that is precious gift that you can share with others.

And when you think about the sounds that comes out of your mouth, and the words that you speak from your completely unique standpoint, know that the sounds of your words are a vibration with their own unique frequency. The breath that is yours so unconditionally, vibrates against your vocal chords, and a vibrational sound comes out of your mouth. This vibration travels through time and space to the eardrums of your audience; when it hits their eardrums, the vibration is converted into neural information that travels through the brain of the other person where it is then understood and interpreted as language.

Your voice has the power to create neurochemical reactions in another person. Your unique and wonderful voice deserves to be heard. It is your right as human being to speak and to be heard, knowing that what you say is of value.

And know that when the vibration of your words reaches the eardrum of the other person, and they then process the sound, know that you are not responsible for or in control of *how* your words are interpreted by the other person; your power lies in how you deliver your words.

Power Pose

I invite you now to bring your attention back to the golden circle on your stage where your Protagonist is standing, awaiting their next direction. The Directors now turn their focus towards the Protagonists physical posture and instruct the Protagonist to stand tall, shoulders back with the head up, feet hip width apart, knowing that this posture will allow the Protagonist to breathe fully and openly which in turn enables them to project their voice.

In a lot of movies nowadays, the Protagonist character is often represented as a Superhero and so today we are going to take a bit of inspiration from the world of Superheroes. The Directors now

ask the Protagonist to put their hands into a fist, and put their fists on their hips, just like a superhero would stand. This is called the Power Pose, and it's easy to do and so effective in helping us to feel confident, because holding our body in a certain way can affect how we feel.

So, as you imagine your Protagonist in this pose, I invite you now to stand up and try it with me.

[DEMONSTRATE POWER POSE]

Know that by standing in this position for a few minutes before you go on stage, you can lower your cortisol levels by 25% and increase a feeling of confidence.

[Sit back down].

As you close your eyes, we return our focus back to the stage, we see that the Protagonist is standing in the Power Pose, looking confident and calm. Director [Insert name of C1] now instructs the protagonist to embody the next resource:

This is the resource of giving to others, knowing that the words they speak, or present, are in **service** to the audience. Knowing that it is not about demonstrating *how much they know* about their chosen topic, and more about knowing what information the audience needs to hear and how they can help their audience.

Director [Insert name of C1] also instructs the Protagonist to use the **resource of Storytelling**, knowing that personal anecdotes and descriptive stories can help them connect to their audience, and help their audience to really understand what they have to say.

[Insert name of C1] now asks the Protagonist to reflect on the following resources:

Energy	What type of energy?
	[Participant responses recorded here]
Eye Contact	How will they use eye contact?
	[Participant responses recorded here].
Engaging with Audience	In what way will they engage?
	[Participant responses recorded here].
Any other resources needed?	[Participant responses recorded here].

You become aware that Director Compassion is preparing to give the Protagonist their final resource:

The resource of Permission; permission to make mistakes, permission to get something wrong, permission to get their words jumbled, permission to be imperfect - knowing that making mistakes and errors is a fundamental part of being human, that these are something all humans have in common and in fact being able to show a bit of humility and humour in these situations can often lead to a greater connection with the audience. I invite you to take a moment to consider what it would be like if we gave ourselves this kind of permission, not just when speaking or presenting to others, but in any of life's situations. **What would life be like?**

[Participant responses recorded here].

As your Protagonist stands in the shimmering golden circle upon your stage, you notice how strong and confident they look as they stand there knowingly equipped with the resources they need to confidently present to others; the calm breath, the strong posture, warmed-up voice, high energy, open, approachable, smiling, ready to engage their audience with and storytelling, knowing what they say is of value, comfortable with making a mistake and able to connect to the audience with humour.

Notice how the Protagonist feels in this moment.

You notice now that [Insert name of C1] and Compassion have joined the Protagonist in the golden circle, and they too have now become bathed in the magical golden light.

Imagine now that you have also joined [Insert name of C1] Compassion, and your Protagonist inside the golden circle, where you too have now been bathed in golden light. You slowly look round the circle at each of your characters, [Insert name of C1] Compassion, and your Protagonist. It is thanks to your unique life experiences and your wonderful imagination that these characters exist and have been brought to life to share their gifts.

And as you stand here today on your magical stage, standing in the golden circle with your unique characters, know that although fictional, these characters also represent aspects of the wonderful human being that you are. The courageous honesty of [Insert name of C1], the kindness and empathy of Compassion, the strength and confidence of the Protagonist – know that all of these wonderful traits reside within you; that all of these qualities exist within you and know that it is possible for you to connect in and access these traits and qualities when preparing to speak or present to groups.

And perhaps today you don't feel fully connected to these inner qualities, and that is okay too, the most important part is being open to the fact that it's possible. Take a moment now to notice how you feel.

You notice now that the curtain is once again coming down and you know that it is time to leave this magical space. Making your way to the aisle, you thank your Inner Stage of Positivity for its support, and you thank yourself for creating such a wonderful positive, safe space to retreat to and for working here today towards building your confidence.

You find yourself walking up the aisle towards the exit. Closing the door behind you, you once again find yourself at the 5 ornate steppingstones. As I count with each steppingstone, you begin to return into the room.

Five: beginning to feel more alert...bring your awareness back to your breathing.

Four: noticing the feel of the bed/chair beneath you.

Three: gently start moving again ...wiggling your fingers and toes and having a little stretch.

Two: you are now fully aware of room that you are in.

One: eyes open, feeling relaxed and alert.

Appendix 6: Session Four Episodic Simulation Script – Template for all participants

The following script is a template that was used for each participant. It was created in such a way that enabled standardisation whilst allowing space for the nine individual scenarios personal to each participant. The individual scenarios can be found in Appendix 7a-7i, pp. 111-136.

We will now prepare now to visit your private, Inner Stage of Positivity, and as we do so today, you will take the final steps on your journey towards embracing that wonderful confidence that has been growing and blossoming within you as we have worked together these past few weeks.

And as we work together today you will once again draw inspiration from your own inner experiences and from your rich and fertile imagination as we create your final scene, safe in the knowledge that there is no right or wrong way to have this experience.

And don't worry if you cannot see or sense anything today, that is perfectly okay; the most important thing is that you are setting the intention right now in this very moment to have this positive experience of speaking confidently to groups of others.

From time to time your thoughts may drift off and distract you... that is quite normal, don't worry. Just gently bring your focus back to your breathing and the sound of my voice.

So, relax and let the power of your wonderful imagination will guide you.

As you continue to relax, you become aware that you are standing on a pathway, and up ahead you can once again see or sense your magical inner theatre.

As you stand there gazing at your theatre up ahead, you notice that the entire building is once again surrounded by a sparkling golden light, radiating, and inviting.

You look down and notice that your feet are now standing on your beautiful stepping stones, and you can feel the positive energy of the theatre pulling you towards it like a magnet.

As you feel your foot touch the **first steppingstone**, a wave of positivity passes through your entire body.

You step onto the **next steppingstone**, moving closer to the theatre, you feel a sense of calm.

Reaching the **third steppingstone**, you feel a deeper sense of relaxation which spreads through your entire body as you step on **the fourth stone**, moving ever closer to the magical golden theatre.

And now, as you reach the **fifth and final steppingstone**, you arrive at the doorway to your theatre, noticing that you too, become bathed in a beautiful golden light. Feeling safe and relaxed, you are ready to enter this magical theatre.

As you open the door and step inside your auditorium of positivity... you take a moment now to fully notice the space.

And as you look around this magnificent space, you notice that all the seats in your auditorium are once again filled with balls of vibrant white light. These balls of energy are radiating love and unconditional acceptance towards you and are here to support you today as you perform your final scene.

You take a moment to gaze round at each ball of white energy eager and allow yourself to feel the waves of positivity radiating towards you as they sit there eager to hear what you have to say today, knowing that what you have to say is of great value. They respect you and are here to support you unconditionally.

Now you notice that [Insert name of C1] and Compassion and your Protagonist are also sitting in the auditorium, smiling radiantly at you. They know how hard you have all worked towards this moment, preparing, and equipping yourself with resources needed to speak confidently to groups, and they are so excited to see you thrive as you present today on your stage of strength and positivity. They have complete faith in you and are excited to see you succeed. They are rooting for you, alongside all the vibrant white balls of energy that fill every seat in the auditorium.

You become aware of a door at the bottom of the auditorium that leads you to the backstage area. You open the door and find yourself in a corridor which is glowing in radiant golden light. As you walk along this golden corridor you notice that you too become bathed in this radiant golden shimmering light.

Arriving at the doorway to the backstage area, you open it and as you cross the threshold you feel a wave of excitement pass through your entire body, knowing that you are about to experience what it feels like to confidently present to others.

You find yourself standing in the wings of the theatre, where you will now begin some final preparations. You become aware of the skills and qualities that you have developed over these past few weeks. The resources and qualities that are within you, that you have worked to access and bring to life.

The ability to use your breath in a way that brings a sense of calm and focus, knowing that breathing slowly and deeply into your diaphragm will help you feel grounded.

The knowledge of how to warm up your facial muscles and vocal chords, knowing that doing so will help you form the words you want to speak and will give you the volume you need to be heard.

The awareness that changing your posture can bring about a sense of strength and power and you as you acknowledge this skill, you notice that you are now standing tall, and upright, with your shoulders back and your head held high. And as you continue to breathe slowly and deeply, you feel this strength within you building.

You notice now that your energy levels are beginning to rise, and you are now feeling a sense of excitement building. Knowing that you have valuable information to share with others, knowing that what you say is valid and of great importance. Knowing that sharing your information is an act of service to your audience and knowing that your supportive audience does not need or expect you to have perfection.

As you stand there in the wings and feel your excitement building, you are overcome with a sense of readiness. You know that you have worked hard to prepare for this moment: it is time to deliver your final scene.

And so, you step on to your magnificent stage of confidence, and as you do so, you notice that the stage crew have transformed the set:

[Individual participant scenarios were inserted here. These are located in Appendix 7a – 7i, pp. 111-136.]

You notice that the image is beginning to fade now, and you are once standing on your stage. You turn to face your auditorium where you notice that [Insert name of C1] Compassion and your Protagonist have huge smiles and are beaming up at you full of pride and achievement. You become aware now that the entire auditorium filled with those radiant balls of white light has now erupted into vibrant round of applause, as you step forward and take a well-deserved bow.

Take a moment now to notice how good it feels as they all celebrate your successful Final Scene, knowing that you have performed it so well. Knowing that they are applauding all the wonderful work you have done here these past few weeks to improve your confidence when speaking or presenting to groups. Notice how good it feels to take this positive action.

And now, the curtain begins to come down for the final time, and you walk down a small set of steps at the side of the stage and into the auditorium of positivity that is still cheering for you. You walk up the aisle bathing in this radiant positivity that is all for you. When you reach the door, you turn around for one final look today, knowing that you can return to this place of your creation any time; knowing that when you return you will always be accepted unconditionally, you will always be supported; knowing that you will always succeed.

You take a moment now to thank this wonderful space of your creation for working with you to build your confidence when speaking with others. And you thank yourself for creating this magnificent space and the wonderful characters that have joined you on your journey.

You now step through the door, closing it behind you, you once again find yourself at the 5 ornate steppingstones. As I count with each steppingstone, you begin to return back into the room.

Five: beginning to feel more alert...bring your awareness back to your breathing.

Four: noticing the feel of the bed/chair beneath you.

Three: gently start moving again ...wiggling your fingers and toes and having a little stretch.

Two: you are now fully aware of room that you are in.

One: eyes open, feeling relaxed and alert.

Appendix 7a: Session Four Episodic Simulation Script – Participant 1

P1 Scenario: Addressing a group of walkers as their mountain guide.

And so, you step on to your magnificent stage of confidence, and as you do so, you notice that the stage crew have transformed the set:

You now become aware that you are in the familiar carpark at the foot of Ben Nevis on a bright and sunny summer morning. You become aware that a small group of happy hikers are gathered around the picnic table that sits in front of the little bridge. This group of happy hikers are excitedly waiting for your arrival, knowing that with all your knowledge, skills, and prior experience of climbing Ben Nevis, that you are the perfect person to be their mountain guide.

You walk confidently across the carpark towards your group of hikers and greet them with a warm relaxed smile.

Feeling secure and relaxed, you can make eye contact with each of them, smiling as you do so. And as you look and smile each of them, you notice they are giving you a feeling of warmth and acceptance. You sense that they like you, and that they want to listen to what you have to say, knowing that you have so much practical experience that will really benefit them.

You know in this moment that they are on your side.

As you continue to warmly look round at your group of hikers you now introduce yourself for the benefit of those who have never before had the opportunity to connect with the completely unique and magnificent being that is you.

You notice your breathing is calm and flowing effortlessly. Your posture conveys the right balance of strength and relaxation as your strong legs support you.

You begin now to speak those words that you have come here today to express and as you do so, you notice your mouth is moist and your facial muscles are nice and flexible, allowing you to form the words effortlessly. You speak clearly with the ideal volume.

And as you speak to your group today to prepare them, each of them knows you have information that they don't, and they are fully aware that what you have to say will help them traverse the

mountains safely, and each word you speak will also help them get to know you better, making it easy to trust you.

They value the fact that you will share your knowledge and wisdom, your personal experiences and interests with them.

As you speak to your group, you feel at ease and can present your ideas and thoughts, opinions, and observations, knowing that you deserve to be heard and that your contribution is valid and of value; you are the authority on what you have to say based on your professional observations each time you have walked on Scotland's highest mountain.

You engage with your group using open body language with a friendly but professional demeanor, telling relevant personal stories and anecdotes with a sprinkle of humour, all of which strengthens the connection with them.

You speak sincerely, with integrity, in a natural conversational way that makes you approachable and relatable completely free in your-expression knowing that there is only one you in this entire universe and you deserve to express yourself in your own unique way. You are the best person in the world to be you and in doing so, you naturally build up the like and trust, which is so important when connecting with your group.

As you look round at your group, you notice that you have their full undivided attention; that they are fully receiving what you have to say with respect and gratitude and are smiling at you with warmth enthusiasm and acceptance. You feel safe in the knowledge that they don't expect you to be perfect, knowing that if you were to get some words jumbled, it would only make warm to you even more, for they value your humility and gracious humour and your ability to laugh it off. And in doing so, you would be demonstrating what it looks like to show self-compassion.

And as you continue to connect with your group of hikers, your friendly and open demeanour makes them feel comfortable enough to ask you questions about Ben Nevis and the journey ahead, and you feel comfortable enough to answer those questions, feeling safe in your connection with them. And if someone asks you a question and you don't know the answer, you warmly thank them for their question and tell them you will research the answer and get back to them at a later time, safe

in the knowledge that when you find the answer to their question, your already vast knowledge will have expanded even more.

You look round at your group and notice that you feel satisfied, confident, and proud of what you have achieved this morning in this pre-climb briefing. You have used the resources that you have recently been building in our sessions to engage confidently with others and in doing so, you have been received with respect and kindness.

As your pre-climb briefing draws to a close, and you prepare to begin your journey up Ben Nevis, you thank them for listening, and you feel a sense of achievement and accomplishment knowing that you have given them the best information and formed a connection with them and sense of trust which will help ensure their safety on Ben Nevis. Your group begins to make their final adjustments to their rucksacks and walking equipment and you begin to lead them over the small bridge, as you all head off to embrace the adventure of the day.

Appendix 7b: Session Four Episodic Simulation Script – Participant 2

P2 Scenario: Delivering a medical handover in a hospital ward.

And so, you step on to your magnificent stage of confidence, and as you do so, you notice that the stage crew have transformed the set:

Into a hospital ward that you recognise from your placements. You notice the bright lights and bustling sound of activity all around you. As you take a moment to look around and observe this scene, you become aware that up ahead of you a group your colleagues are now beginning to assemble, preparing to give and receive the patient handover information.

You walk confidently towards your fellow colleagues and greet them with a warm relaxed smile. Feeling secure and relaxed, you can make eye contact with each of them, smiling as you do so. And as you look and smile each of them, you notice they are giving you a feeling of warmth and acceptance. You sense that they like you, and that they want to listen to what you have to say. You know in this moment that they are on your side.

As you continue to warmly look round at your group, it is now your turn to speak; you now introduce yourself for the benefit of the staff who have never before met you on the ward, who have before had the opportunity to connect with the completely unique and magnificent nurse that is you. You notice your breathing is calm and flowing effortlessly. Your posture conveys the right balance of strength and relaxation as your strong legs support you.

You begin now to speak those important words that you have come to the handover to express, and as you do so, you notice your mouth is moist and your facial muscles are nice and flexible, allowing you to form the words effortlessly. You speak clearly with the ideal volume.

And as you speak to your colleagues, they know you have information that they don't, and they are fully aware that what you have to say will help and inform them.

They value the fact that you will share your knowledge and professional insights with them. As you speak to medical colleagues you feel at ease and can present your ideas and thoughts, opinions, and observations, knowing that you deserve to be heard and that your contribution is

valid and of value; you are the authority on what you have to say based on your professional observations during your shift today.

You engage with your colleagues using open body language with a friendly but professional demeanour, telling relevant details and perhaps even with a sprinkle of humour where appropriate, all of which strengthens the connection with your colleagues.

You speak sincerely, with integrity, in a natural conversational way that makes you approachable and relatable, completely free in your-expression knowing that there is only one you in this entire universe and you deserve to express yourself in your own unique way. You are the best person in the world to be you and in doing so, you naturally build up the like and trust, which is so important when connecting with your colleagues.

As you look round at your medical colleagues you notice that you have their full undivided attention; that they are fully receiving what you have to say with respect and gratitude and are smiling at you with warmth enthusiasm and acceptance. You feel safe in the knowledge that they don't expect you to be perfect, knowing that if you were to get some words jumbled, it would only make warm to you even more, for they value your humility and gracious humour and your ability to laugh it off. And in doing so, you would be demonstrating what it looks like to show self-compassion whilst remaining professional.

And as you continue to connect with your colleagues, your friendly and open demeanour makes them feel comfortable enough to ask you questions about your observations and you feel comfortable enough to answer those questions fully, feeling safe in your connection with them.

And if someone asks you a question and you don't know the answer, you warmly thank them for their question and tell them you will obtain the answer and get back to them at a later time, safe in the knowledge that when you find the answer to their question, your already vast knowledge and experience will have expanded even more.

You look round at your colleagues on the ward today and notice that you feel satisfied, confident, and proud of what you have achieved today in this handover. You have used the resources that you have recently been building to engage confidently with your fellow staff and in doing so, you have been received with respect and kindness.

As the handover draws to a close, you thank your colleagues and you feel a sense of achievement and accomplishment, knowing that you have communicated in a confident and professional way. You notice now that your colleagues all begin to disperse and as you watch them walk up the corridor, the scene begins to fade.

Appendix 7c: Session Four Episodic Simulation Script – Participant 3

P3 Scenario: Delivering a workshop.

And so, you step on to your magnificent stage of confidence, and as you do so, you notice that the stage crew have transformed the set:

Into a large workshop space with a seated area to one side and an activity space on the other. The set is bright and illuminated, welcoming and warm.

Take your place at front of the seated area and notice that your participants are now filing into the space. You smile a warm welcoming smile at them as they take their seats and settle in. Once the last of your participants settles in, it is now time for you to begin your workshop.

You greet your workshop participants with a warm relaxed smile.

Feeling secure and relaxed, you can make eye contact with each of them, smiling as you do so. And as you look and smile round at each of them, you notice they are giving you a feeling of warmth and acceptance. You sense that they like you, and that they want to listen to what you have to say.

You know in this moment that they are on your side.

As you continue to warmly look round at your group of participants you now introduce yourself for the benefit of those who have never before had the opportunity to connect with the completely unique and magnificent being that is you.

You notice your breathing is calm and flowing effortlessly. Your posture conveys the right balance of strength and relaxation as your strong legs support you.

You begin now to speak those words that you have come here today to express and as you do so, you notice your mouth is moist and your facial muscles are nice and flexible, allowing you to form the words and articulate them effortlessly. You speak clearly, projecting at the ideal volume.

And as you speak today, your participants know you have information that they don't, and they are fully aware that what you have to say will not only help them but will also allow them to get to know you better.

They value the fact that you will share your knowledge and wisdom, and relevant personal experiences with them.

As you speak to your group of participants, you feel at ease and are able to present your ideas and thoughts, opinions and observations, knowing that you deserve to be heard and that your contribution is valid and of value; you are the authority on what you have to say based on your professional observations and experiences gained throughout your varied and dynamic career in theatre and education.

You engage with your participants using open body language with a friendly but professional demeanour, telling relevant personal stories and anecdotes with a sprinkle of humour, able to engage with all ages and levels of learning, education, and maturity; all of which strengthens the connection with your participants.

You speak sincerely, with integrity, in a natural conversational way that makes you approachable and relatable completely free in your-expression knowing that there is only one you in this entire universe and you deserve to express yourself in your own unique way. You are the best person in the world to be you and in doing so, you naturally build up the like and trust, which is so important when connecting with your participants.

As you look round at your group you notice that you have their full undivided attention; that they are fully receiving what you have to say with respect and gratitude and are smiling at you with warmth enthusiasm and acceptance. You feel safe in the knowledge that they don't expect you to be perfect, knowing that if you were to get some words jumbled, it would only make warm to you even more, for they value your humility and gracious humour and your ability to laugh it off. And in doing so, you would be demonstrating what it looks like to show self-compassion.

And as you continue to connect with your participants, your vibrant, friendly, and open demeanour makes them feel comfortable enough to ask you questions related to the workshop, and you feel comfortable enough to answer those questions, feeling safe in your connection with them.

And if someone asks you a question and you don't know the answer, you warmly thank them for their question and tell them you will research the answer and get back to them at a later time, safe

in the knowledge that when you find the answer to their question, your already vast knowledge will have expanded even more.

You look round at your participants and see that they are contentedly enjoying themselves, relishing the fact that you are teaching them something new, and you notice that you feel satisfied, confident, and proud of what you have achieved today during this workshop. You have used the resources that you have recently been building to engage confidently with your group, and in doing so, you have been received with respect and kindness.

As your workshop draws to a close, you thank your group of participants for listening and sharing this experience with you today. You feel a sense of achievement and accomplishment.

Appendix 7d: Session Four Episodic Simulation Script – Participant 4

P4 Scenario: Delivering a motivation speech.

And so, you step on to your magnificent stage of confidence, and as you do so, you notice that the stage crew have transformed the set:

You now notice that fixed to the back of stage is a giant screen displaying your name in giant letters, next to your professional headshot, and the title of your talk. At either side of the screen are giant vertical banners displaying your unique business logo.

A member of the stage crew comes to give your mic and battery pack one final check; you are all set to go. Over the loudspeaker you can hear your intro music begin to play, and the audience breaks into a thunderous round of applause; this is what they have been waiting for. And to the sound of their thunderous applause of anticipation, you make your entrance.

You stride confidently towards your audience and greet them with a warm relaxed smile. Feeling secure and relaxed, you make eye contact with them, smiling as you do so. And as you look and smile each of them, you sense they are giving you a feeling of warmth and acceptance. You sense that they instantly like you, and that they want to listen to what you have to say. You know in this moment that your audience are on your side.

As that clapping starts to settle and you continue to warmly look around your audience you now introduce yourself for the benefit of those who have never had the opportunity to connect with the completely unique and magnificent being that is you.

You notice your breathing is calm and flowing effortlessly. Your posture conveys the right balance of strength and relaxation as your strong legs support you.

You begin now to speak those words that you have come here today to express and as you do so, you notice your mouth is moist and your facial muscles are nice and flexible, allowing you to form the words effortlessly. You speak clearly with the ideal volume.

And as you speak today, your audience knows you have information that they don't, and they are fully aware that what you have to say will help enhance their knowledge and personal development and will also help them get to know themselves better as you present your information in such a thought-provoking way.

They value the fact that you will share your knowledge and wisdom, personal experiences and interests with them, and this helps them get to know you better too, which fosters a deeper sense of connection between you and your audience.

As you speak today, you feel at ease and are able to present your ideas and thoughts, opinions and observations, knowing that you deserve to be heard and that your contribution is valid and of value; you are the authority on what you have to say based on your professional observations and experiences gained throughout your career and also your rich and varied life experiences.

You engage with your audience using open body language with a friendly but professional demeanor, telling relevant personal stories and anecdotes with humour which brings laughter and positive energy to the talk, all of which strengthens the connection.

You speak sincerely, with integrity, in a natural conversational way that makes you approachable and relatable but is at times powerful and motivational. You are completely free in your-expression knowing that there is only one you in this entire universe and you deserve to express yourself in your own unique way. You are the best person in the world to be you and in doing so, you naturally build up the like and trust, which is so important when connecting with your audience.

As you look around the auditorium, you notice that you have their full undivided attention; that they are fully receiving what you have to say with respect and gratitude and are smiling at you with warmth enthusiasm and acceptance. You feel safe in the knowledge that they don't expect you to be perfect, knowing that if you were to get some words jumbled, it would only make warm to you even more, for they value your humility and gracious humour and your ability to laugh it off. And in doing so, you would be demonstrating what it looks like to show self-compassion whilst maintaining professionalism.

And as you continue to connect with the members of your audience, your friendly and open demeanour makes them feel comfortable enough to ask you questions about, and you feel comfortable enough to answer those questions, feeling safe in your connection with them.

And if someone asks you a question and you don't know the answer, you warmly thank them for their question and tell them you will research the answer and get back to them at a later time, safe in the knowledge that when you find the answer to their question, your already vast knowledge will have expanded even more.

You look round at your audience and notice that you feel satisfied, confident, and proud of what you have achieved today in this magnificent inspirational and motivational talk. You have used the resources that you have recently been building to speak confidently with and in doing so, you have been received with respect and kindness.

As your talk draws to a close, you thank your audience for listening, and sharing this experience with you today. You feel a sense of achievement and accomplishment knowing that you were able to make a difference by sharing your knowledge and wisdom with them, knowing that each member will leave the auditorium with an expanded awareness thanks to you and the way you have presented here today.

Appendix 7e: Session Four Episodic Simulation Script – Participant 5

P5 Scenario: Introducing herself to a new social gardening group.

And so, you step on to your magnificent stage of confidence, and as you do so, you notice that the stage crew have transformed the set:

Into a welcoming room inside a community centre, where your local gardening club are hosting a meeting. You pause for a moment to notice this bright and welcoming room, the windows letting in the natural light of the warm sun, with encouraging golden rays streaming in to illuminate the space.

You notice a circle of chairs in the centre of the room, some of which have people sitting in them already and some of which are vacant waiting to be filled. You can hear the buzz of vibrant chatter amongst members of the club, and you get the sense that this is a friendly group of people who really enjoy welcoming new members into the fold.

You now walk confidently towards the circle and take a seat, greeting those you pass with a warm relaxed smile. The person next to you smiles warmly and introduces themselves and you both share a few warm pleasantries as the rest of the group take their seats.

You become aware that the organiser has now begun to address the group and explains that today the club has the pleasure of welcoming a brand-new member. She invites you now to introduce yourself to the group and you notice that group smile warmly and enthusiastically with a mixture of waves and welcomes.

Feeling secure and relaxed, you can make eye contact with each of them as you look round the circle, smiling as you do so. And as you look and smile each of them, you notice they are giving you a feeling of warmth and acceptance. You sense that they like you, and that they want to listen to what you have to say.

You know in this moment that they are on your side.

As you continue to warmly look round at your fellow gardeners, you now introduce yourself for the benefit of those who have never before had the opportunity to connect with the completely unique and magnificent being that is you.

You notice your breathing is calm and flowing effortlessly. Your posture conveys the right balance of strength and relaxation as you sit in your chair.

You begin now to speak those words of introduction and as you do so, you notice your mouth is moist and your facial muscles are nice and flexible, allowing you to form the words effortlessly. You speak clearly with the ideal volume.

And as you speak today, the group knows you have information that they don't, and they are fully aware that what you tell them about yourself will help them get to know you better.

They love to welcome new members and value the fact that you will share a little about your life and your interests, and your mutual interest of gardening with them, with them.

As you speak to the group, you feel at ease and can tell them about who you are, why you are there, things you enjoy, knowing that you deserve to be heard and that your contribution to the group is valid and of great value to them.

You engage with the group using open body language with a friendly demeanor, perhaps telling a little anecdote with a sprinkle of humour, all of which strengthens the connection with your new fellow gardeners.

You speak sincerely, with integrity, in a natural conversational way that makes you approachable and relatable completely free in your-expression knowing that there is only one you in this entire universe and you deserve to express yourself in your own unique way. You are the best person in the world to be you and in doing so, you naturally build up the like and trust, which is so important when connecting with a new group of friends.

As you look round at the group, you notice that you have their full undivided attention; that they are fully receiving what you have to say with respect and gratitude and are smiling at you with warmth enthusiasm and acceptance. You feel safe in the knowledge that they don't expect you to be anything other than the unique and radiant person that you are.

And as you continue to connect with your fellow gardeners, your naturally friendly and open demeanour makes them feel comfortable enough to ask you questions about your mutual love of gardening, and you feel happy to answer those questions, feeling safe in your connection with them.

In this moment, you notice that you feel satisfied, confident, and proud of what you have achieved today. You have used the resources that you have recently been building to engage confidently with a new group and in doing so, you have been received with respect and kindness. You have been embraced into this new group with whom you have so much in common.

As your vibrant introduction draws to a close, the group thank you for being open and sharing with them today, and you feel a sense of achievement and accomplishment at the having the confidence to be your magnificent radiant self.

Appendix 7f: Session Four Episodic Simulation Script – Participant 6

P6 Scenario: Delivering a Ted Talk.

And so, you step on to your magnificent stage of confidence, and as you do so, you notice that the stage crew have transformed the set:

You now notice that standing at the back of stage are the three familiar giant red letters of the TED sign sitting below a giant projector screen displaying your name and the title of your talk. On the centre of the stage, where your golden circle lay before, is now the giant red Ted Talk circle.

A member of the stage crew comes to give your mic and battery pack one final check; you are all set to go. Over the loudspeaker you can hear your name being introduced, and the audience breaks into a thunderous round of applause; this is what they have been waiting for. And to the sound of their applause, you make your entrance.

You stride confidently towards your audience and greet them with a warm relaxed smile.

Feeling secure and relaxed, you can make eye contact with them, smiling as you do so. And as you look and smile each of them, you sense they are giving you a feeling of warmth and acceptance. You sense that they instantly like you, and that they want to listen to what you have to say.

You know in this moment that your audience are on your side.

As that clapping starts to settle and you continue to warmly look around your audience you now introduce yourself for the benefit of those who have never before had the opportunity to connect with the completely unique and magnificent being that is you.

You notice your breathing is calm and flowing effortlessly. Your posture conveys the right balance of strength and relaxation as your strong legs support you.

You begin now to speak those words that you have come here today to express and as you do so, you notice your mouth is moist and your facial muscles are nice and flexible, allowing you to form the words effortlessly. You speak clearly with the ideal volume.

And as you speak today, your audience knows you have information that they don't, and they are fully aware that what you have to say will help enhance their knowledge and will also help them get to know themselves better as you present your information in such a thought-provoking way.

They value the fact that you will share your knowledge, wisdom, personal experiences and interests with them, and this helps them get to know you better too, which fosters a deeper sense of connection between you and your audience.

As you speak today, you feel at ease and are able to present your ideas and thoughts, opinions and observations, knowing that you deserve to be heard and that your contribution is valid and of value; you are the authority on what you have to say based on your professional observations and experiences gained throughout your career.

You engage with your audience using open body language with a friendly but professional demeanour, telling relevant personal stories and anecdotes with humour which brings laughter and positive energy to the talk, all of which strengthens the connection.

You speak sincerely, with integrity, in a natural conversational way that makes you approachable and relatable completely free in your-expression knowing that there is only one you in this entire universe and you deserve to express yourself in your own unique way. You are the best person in the world to be you and in doing so, you naturally build up the like and trust, which is so important when connecting with your audience.

As you look around the auditorium, you notice that you have their full undivided attention; that they are fully receiving what you have to say with respect and gratitude and are smiling at you with warmth enthusiasm and acceptance. You feel safe in the knowledge that they don't expect you to be perfect, knowing that if you were to get some words jumbled, it would only make warm to you even more, for they value your humility and gracious humour and your ability to laugh it off. And in doing so, you would be demonstrating what it looks like to show self-compassion whilst maintaining professionalism.

And as you continue to connect with the members of your audience, your friendly and open demeanour makes them feel comfortable enough to ask you questions about your area of interest,

and you feel comfortable enough to answer those questions, feeling safe in your connection with them.

And if someone asks you a question and you don't know the answer, you warmly thank them for their question and tell them you will research the answer and get back to them at a later time, safe in the knowledge that when you find the answer to their question, your already vast knowledge will have expanded even more.

You look round at your audience and notice that you feel satisfied, confident, and proud of what you have achieved today in this magnificent TED Talk. You have used the resources that you have recently been building to speak confidently with and in doing so, you have been received with respect and kindness.

As your TED Talk draws to a close, you thank your audience for listening, and sharing this experience with you today. You feel a sense of achievement and accomplishment knowing that you were able to make a difference by sharing your knowledge and wisdom with them, knowing that each member will leave the auditorium with an expanded awareness thanks to you and the way you have presented here today.

Appendix 7g: Session Four Episodic Simulation Script – Participant 7

P7 Scenario: Attending an acting audition.

And so, you step on to your magnificent stage of confidence, and as you do so, you notice that the stage crew have transformed the set:

Into an audition room. You notice that the director and casting director are sitting at a table. Next to them is the performance space with a backdrop, and a singular chair positioned in front of a camera which is operated by a friendly looking cameraman.

You walk confidently towards the director and casting director and greet them with a warm relaxed smile.

Feeling secure and relaxed, you can make eye contact with each of them, smiling as you do so. And as you look and smile each of them, you notice they are giving you a feeling of warmth and acceptance. You sense that they like you, and that they want you to succeed in your audition.

You know in this moment that they are on your side.

As you continue to warmly look at the director and casting director, you now introduce yourself for the benefit of those who have never before had the opportunity to connect with the completely unique and magnificent being that is you.

You notice your breathing is calm and flowing effortlessly. Your posture conveys the right balance of strength and relaxation as your strong legs support you.

The director invites you to tell them a little bit about yourself, and as you speak, you feel at ease and are able to share your experiences, thoughts and opinions, knowing that you deserve to be heard. Knowing that what you say is valid and of value.

You engage with the director and the casting director using open body language with a friendly but professional demeanor, telling relevant personal stories and anecdotes with a sprinkle of humour, and you notice this strengthens the connection with them. They know you have information about

yourself that they don't, and they are fully aware that what you have to say will help them get to know you better.

You speak sincerely, with integrity, in a natural conversational way that makes you approachable and relatable completely free in your-expression knowing that there is only one you in this entire universe and you deserve to express yourself in your own unique way. You are the best person in the world to be you, and also that you are the best actor for the part that you are auditioning for today.

The director invites you to take a seat in the audition space and you walk confidently across to the chair that sits against the backdrop. Taking a seat, you adopt a relaxed and confident posture and notice the excitement that is bubbling inside, knowing that you have rehearsed and are fully prepared for this audition.

You begin now to perform the script that you know so well from memory and as you do so, you notice your mouth is moist and your facial muscles are nice and flexible, allowing you to form the words effortlessly. You speak with clarity and can project your voice at the ideal volume, with perfect pacing and vocal dynamics.

And as you perform today, you can convey the emotional journey of the character in such an authentic way, drawing in not only those in the room watching but those who later watch the replay. You are a natural in front of the camera.

You become aware that that you have their full undivided attention; that they are fully receiving what your performance, willing you to succeed.

As your performance comes to an end you see the director and casting director smiling at you with warm enthusiasm and acceptance, safe in the knowledge that they have found their ideal actor, and they offer you the part right there on the spot.

You notice that you feel excited, satisfied, confident, and proud of what you have achieved today in this excellent audition. You have used the resources that you have recently been building to engage confidently during your audition, and in doing so, you have been received with respect and admiration.

As your audition draws to a close, you thank the director and casting director for the opportunity letting them know that you look forward to working with them. You feel a sense of achievement and accomplishment.

As you turn to leave the audition room, you once again become aware of the stage that you are standing on.

Appendix 7h: Session Four Episodic Simulation Script – Participant 8

P8 Scenario: Live social media broadcast.

And so, you step on to your magnificent stage of confidence, and as you do so, you notice that the stage crew have transformed the set:

Into a familiar room, where you have set up a home-studio workspace designed to broadcast to your ever-growing audience of followers. As you approach the set, you notice a carefully chosen backdrop that represents who you are with the colours of your brand and logo.

You notice that there are light stands which radiate the ideal combination of brightness and softness that will illuminate you, making you look radiant as you broadcast your message.

And in the middle of the lights, in front of your backdrop is a camera on its stand, ready to record. You approach the backdrop and take a seat in front of the camera. There is a small microphone resting by the camera. You attach it to your clothes where it now rests discretely, and will clearly catch every word you have to speak, reducing any background noise as it does so.

As you settle into a comfortable position on your chair, you hold your head high and your shoulders back, relaxed but confident.

You check your equipment one final time: you are happy with your lighting and your carefully chosen back-drop and your mic is in place. You pause for a moment to take a slow deep breath. Feeling poised, ready and in control, you face your camera lens, and with a confident smile, you are ready to go live.

You greet your virtual audience with a warm relaxed smile.

Feeling secure and relaxed, you can make eye contact with your virtual audience by looking down the lens of the camera, smiling as you do so. And as you look down the lens and smile, you intuitively sense that your viewers are giving you a feeling of warmth and acceptance. You sense that they like you, and that they want to listen to what you have to say.

You know in this moment that they are on your side and have been guided by the universe to hear what you have to say.

As you continue to warmly look at the camera, you now introduce yourself for the benefit of those who have never before had the opportunity to connect with the completely unique and magnificent being that is you.

You notice your breathing is calm and flowing effortlessly. Your posture conveys the right balance of strength and relaxation as the chair supports you.

You begin now to speak those words that you have come here to express and as you do so, you notice your mouth is moist and your facial muscles are nice and flexible, allowing you to form the words effortlessly. You speak clearly with the ideal volume and pacing, with compassion in your tone, allowing your virtual audience to get a deeper sense of your integrity.

And as you speak today, your listeners know you have information that they don't, and they are fully aware that what you have to say will help them on their journey with parenthood, but that it will also help them get to know you better as practitioner and as a person.

They value the fact that you will share your knowledge and wisdom that you have gained from your vast experience with them; this is deeply precious and your virtual audience of followers, although out of sight, are right there with you.

As you speak to the camera, you feel at ease and are able to present your ideas and thoughts, opinions and observations, knowing that you deserve to be heard and that your contribution is valid and of value; you are the authority on what you have to say based on your professional observations not just throughout your professional career but also from your own experiences of motherhood. You engage with your virtual audience using open body language with a friendly but professional demeanor, telling relevant personal stories and anecdotes with a sprinkle of humour all of which strengthens the connection with them.

You speak sincerely, with integrity, [in a natural conversational way that makes you approachable and relatable, completely free in your-expression knowing that there is only one you in this entire universe and you deserve to express yourself in your own unique way. You are the best person in

the world to be you and in doing so, you naturally build up the like and trust, which is so important when connecting with your clients.

As you connect with your virtual audience you completely trust that you have their full undivided attention; that they are fully receiving what you have to say with respect and gratitude and are smiling back at you with warmth enthusiasm and acceptance. You feel safe in the knowledge that your viewers don't expect you to be perfect, knowing that if you were to get some words jumbled, it would only make warm to you even more, for they value your humility and gracious humour and your ability to laugh it off. And in doing so, you would be demonstrating what it looks like to show self-compassion.

And as you continue to connect with your online followers, your friendly and open demeanour makes them feel comfortable enough to ask you questions on the comment feed, about and you feel comfortable enough to answer those questions, feeling safe in your connection with them.

And if someone asks you a question and you don't know the answer, you warmly thank them for their question and tell them you will research the answer and get back to them at a later time, safe in the knowledge that when you find the answer to their question, your already vast knowledge will have expanded even more.

You look down the lens and notice that you feel satisfied, confident, and proud of what you have achieved today in this live broadcast. You have used the resources that you have recently been building to engage confidently with your virtual audience and in doing so, you know have been received with respect and kindness.

As your live broadcast draws to a close, you thank your viewers for watching, and sharing this experience with you today, and as you now conclude your live feed, you feel a sense of achievement and accomplishment.

You notice now that the lights on the set begin to dim, indicating the end of the scene. And as they bring your set into darkness, you step off your chair and walk towards the front of your stage to face your auditorium of positivity.

Appendix 7i: Session Four Episodic Simulation Script – Participant 9

P9 Scenario: Presenting at a team meeting.

And so, you step on to your magnificent stage of confidence, and as you do so, you notice that the stage crew have transformed the set:

Which now resembles a familiar team meeting space that you recognise from your place of work. As you look around the space, you notice your colleagues sitting chatting, settling in for the meeting ahead, and awaiting your arrival.

You greet them with a warm relaxed smile.

Feeling secure and relaxed, you can make eye contact with each of them, smiling as you do so. And as you look and smile each of them, you notice they are giving you a feeling of warmth and acceptance. You sense that they like you, and that they want to listen to what you have to say.

You know in this moment that they are on your side.

As you continue to warmly look round at your colleagues gathered here today, you now introduce yourself for the benefit of those who have never before had the opportunity to connect with the completely unique and magnificent being that is you. You notice your breathing is calm and flowing effortlessly. Your posture conveys the right balance of strength and relaxation as your strong legs support you.

You begin now to speak those words that you have come here today to express and as you do so, you notice your mouth is moist and your facial muscles are nice and flexible, allowing you to form the words effortlessly. You speak clearly with the ideal volume.

And as you speak today, your colleagues know you have information that they don't, and they are fully aware that what you have to say will help them with their professional responsibilities.

They value the fact that you will share your knowledge and wisdom personal experiences and interests with them.

As you speak to your colleagues, you feel at ease and can present your ideas and thoughts, opinions and observations, knowing that you deserve to be heard and that your contribution is valid and of

value; you are the authority on what you have to say based on your professional observations during your shift today.

You engage with your listeners using open body language with a friendly but professional demeanor, telling relevant personal stories and anecdotes with a sprinkle of humour, and perhaps using the projector to display some interesting visual aids all of which strengthens the connection with those here today.

You speak sincerely, with integrity, in a natural conversational way that makes you approachable and relatable, completely free in your-expression knowing that there is only one you in this entire universe and you deserve to express yourself in your own unique way. You are the best person in the world to be you.

As you look round, you notice that you have their full undivided attention; that they are fully receiving what you have to say with respect and gratitude and are smiling at you with warmth enthusiasm and acceptance. You feel safe in the knowledge that they don't expect you to be perfect, knowing that if you were to get some words jumbled, it would only make warm to you even more, for they value your humility and gracious humour and your ability to laugh it off. And in doing so, you would be demonstrating what it looks like to show self-compassion.

And as you continue to connect with your colleagues, your friendly and open demeanour makes them feel comfortable enough to ask you questions and you feel comfortable enough to answer those questions, feeling safe in your connection with them.

And if someone asks you a question and you don't know the answer, you warmly thank them for their question and tell them you will research the answer and get back to them at a later time, safe in the knowledge that when you find the answer to their question, your already vast knowledge will have expanded even more.

You notice that you feel satisfied, confident, and proud of what you have achieved today in this team meeting. You have used the resources that you have recently been building to engage confidently with your colleagues and in doing so, you have been received with respect and kindness. As the team meeting draws to a close, you thank everyone for listening, and sharing this experience with you today. You feel a sense of achievement and accomplishment.

Appendix 8: Session 5 Interview Questions

Introductory Questions

Questions
In your own words, tell me about why you chose to take part in the study?
Reflecting on the project as a whole, tell me what the experience has been like for you?

Inner Stage of Positivity

At the beginning of the project, we used Guided Visualisation to create your '**Inner Stage of Positivity**' which served as the workspace for the exercises.

Questions
Tell me about this experience.
In what way, if any, has working from this imaginary inner world impacted your journey towards increasing confidence when speaking or presenting to groups?

Self-Awareness

Questions
Has taking part in the study led you to gain any new insights or awareness's about yourself?
If yes, please share.
Have you gotten to know yourself better during this project?
If yes, in what way?

Meet the Cast: Character Creation

As part of the study, you were invited to use your own lived experiences as inspiration to create 3 characters; a character who was uncomfortable with public speaking, a Compassionate character and a Protagonist who enjoyed public speaking.

Questions

How this experience was for you?

In what way, if any, has this exercise in particular impacted your journey towards increasing self-awareness?

Did you discover anything about yourself during this process?

If yes, please share.

Confidence Reflection

Questions

Do you feel that participating in the study has influenced your levels of confidence when speaking with groups?

If yes, in what way?

On a scale of 1-10 how confident do you feel when speaking or presenting to groups of people?

(Please circle)

0 – Not confident at all / 10 – Extremely confident

Participant	Initial Score	Current Score

Any further comments?

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Appendix 9: Cast List of Created Characters

Participant	C1 Description	Protagonist Description	Compassion Description
P1	James, male, mid-50's, dressed in a pale green British Army World War II Uniform.	Male, late 40's, wearing the same British Army World War II uniform as James, described as being taller than the others and smiling, with a skip in his walk.	Male, also mid-50's, also dressed in a pale green British Army World War II uniform, wearing leather gloves to indicate a higher rank than the others. Walks confidently.
P2	Emma, female, early 20's, with long blonde hair, dressed in black.	Female, early 20's, described as being bigger than Emma, with a confident stance that is radiating off them, dressed in black.	Female, also early 20's, dressed in white with a gold shimmering light radiating off her.
P3	John, male, mid-40's, 5' 3" tall with hunched posture, wearing glasses and a V-neck sweater.	Female, mid-20's with a confident walk, described as resembling Paula Yates, dressed in a black 1950's full-skirted dress, with little pumps on her feet.	Female, mid-60's, well built with light beige coloured hair, dressed in a blanket shawl with bold black & white Mexican patterns.
P4	Claire, female, 10 years old, 4 foot tall with light brown hair, dressed in a grey school uniform from the 50's era, clutching a jotter to her chest.	Male, 40's with long hair, dressed in colourful clothes, carrying an electric guitar, and described as strutting about confidently.	Female, mid 40's, described as large and Rubenesque, with a big personality and a big heart, dressed in an eye-catching blue top with red flowers, gold earrings and a bangle.
P6	Andrew, male, mid-20s, described as tall and thin, wearing jeans and a white shirt.	Male, 40-50', medium build with short hair, dressed in a black t-shirt.	Male, early 30's, physically big with a little round face and dark hair, dressed in dark jeans and shirt.
P7	Phil, male, early 50's, described as tall and slim with brown hair, wearing grey jeans and black woollen jumper.	Male, early 30's, described as being tall with a good build, handsome, resembling Prince Charming and wearing dark clothes.	Female, early 30's, smiley with wide open arms, dressed in a light blue floaty chiffon dress.
P8 Case Study	Female, 15 years old, with short dark hair, dressed in a school uniform with a navy knee-length skirt, white shirt, maroon blazer, and flat nurse shoes.	Female, late 30's, resembling Gabby Bernstein, dressed in a white shirt and trousers with flat shoes, with a confident walk	Female, 25, described as a Fairy Godmother, with blonde hair, tiara, pink shimmery ball gown.
P9	Blur, female, 10 years old, described as very short and wide with jaw-length blue hair, dressed in a long floor-length skirt.	Female, late 20's, described as tall with confident posture, and dressed in the new Wonder Woman outfit with golden armour.	Female, middle-aged, described as looking like the Fairy Godmother in Cinderella, with dark hair, wearing a purple and light blue cloak with

			the hood up, carrying a hairbrush.
P10	Alan, male, early 20's, described as slim with messy light golden hair, wearing a beige tank top.	Male, early 50's resembling the character 'Snape' played by Alan Rickman, described as assertive.	Female, 40's, with dark hair, dressed in green and purple flowing fabric, wearing patchouli oil, and carrying crystals.